

D4.1

Report on mapping, harmonising and integrating novel data sources for research purposes

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This task has allowed SPES research partners to identify and provide an evaluation of complex and novel data sources and associated methods that can be repurposed for the development of innovative measurement framework.

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Abstract

Sustainability, a complex and multi-dimensional phenomenon at the crossroads of environmental, social, geographical, and economic considerations, becomes increasingly crucial to explore and measure as we work towards a more sustainable future. Over the past decades, the rise of innovative data sources has significantly expanded our ability to assess the various dimensions of sustainability. Thus, this report provides on the one hand a mapping of innovative data sources used to measure the dimensions of sustainability transition and on the other hand an overview of data integration methods which enable the use of this novel data sources for research purposes.

The first part of this research consists in a Large Language Models-enabled distant reading of a large collection of academic texts related to innovative data sources used in the study of sustainability. We developed an expansive operationalization of the notion of sustainability, grounded in the SPES framework, to account for its multi-dimensional and inter-disciplinary character. GPT models have been used at various stages to extract, classify and organise information. The analysis shows which type of innovative data categories have been associated to which dimensions of sustainability. To illustrate this, we also present several selected examples.

The second part of this report explores the evolving domain of data integration methods in official statistics and survey methodology. It investigates the possible methods to reach integration of alternative data sources, e.g., administrative records, satellite data, and web data, highlighting their potential to complement and enrich traditional data sources. It offers insights into the challenges and opportunities associated with data integration, providing a comprehensive overview for a broad audience interested in the evolving landscape of statistical methods.

General introduction

Sustainability is a complex, multi-dimensional phenomenon that lies at the intersection of environmental, social, geographical and economic considerations. As we navigate the path toward a more sustainable future, the need to study and measure the performance of sustainability transitions becomes crucial. In the past decades, the advent of innovative data sources has significantly expanded our ability to gauge the many dimensions of sustainability addressed by the SPES framework (Biggeri et. 2023). The inexorable process of *datafication* (Kitchin, 2022) –i.e., the transformation of more and more domains of society into quantified information ready for collection, processing and circulation, has impacted research practices across fields. Unlike traditional data sources (e.g., surveys and census data), novel data sources are often generated as a by-product of activities of all kinds and are only subsequently (and sometimes creatively) repurposed in innovative ways for research goals. Such a complex and dynamic landscape requires continuous exploration and mapping across disciplinary boundaries, to ensure that both potentials and pitfalls are adequately seized and avoided. Albeit providing unprecedented opportunities, indeed, such new sources of data come with several methodological and epistemological caveats.

Traditional data sources have played a pivotal role in furnishing researchers and practitioners with valuable statistical insights for over 80 years. Their reliability in generating statistics across various domains is fundamental and their role will remain unchanged in the future, at least in those countries where well established statistical offices exist. However, there exists ample opportunity to enrich traditional data by incorporating information from alternative sources. Moreover, various current phenomena such as globalisation, recession, economic growth, climate change, urbanisation, digitalisation, ageing society, conflicts, extreme weather events, and humanitarian crisis and their fast pace and development highlight the need for more timely but at the same time reliable ways to capture their multifaceted nature (Bosco et al., 2022).

This report is structured in two complementary parts. Part 1 focuses on the identification, mapping and illustration of innovative data sources for the study of sustainability transition. It answers the following question: What innovative data sources are currently leveraged to study the many dimensions of sustainability? It consists of exploratory research that leverages Large Language Models (LLMs) to extract, classify and organise information about the use of innovative data sources in the study of sustainability, based on a large corpus of recent academic studies. One of the issues that this analysis highlights is the heterogeneity of data types that can be used for the purpose, and the widespread practice of integrating data of different types. Therefore, Part 2 consists in a systematic review of data integration strategies for the creation of a synthetic dataset and for combining probability and nonprobability samples also in the context of non-conventional data sources. It answers the following questions: What is the state-of-the art in data integration methods? Which existing methods can be leveraged to develop an appropriate harmonisation and integration strategy of both traditional and new data sources? This section aims at providing an overview for a broader audience of the statistical methods developed in the last decades in Official statistics and Survey statistics to deal with data integration issues, at proposing toy/practical examples to illustrate both the issues at stake and the methods suggested to tackle them and supplying available statistical software and packages for their implementation.

PART I

Mapping Innovative Data Sources Across the Many Dimensions of Sustainability Research

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1. Introduction

The study of sustainability spans across several academic fields, such as environmental studies, developmental economics, social and demographic sciences, and geography. Consequently, it relies on data pertaining to diverse domains, such as environmental data, demographic data, economic data, geo-spatial data. Traditional sources of data relevant for sustainability research include national as well as transnational, public as well as private bodies such as statistical offices; universities and research institutes; meteorological services; energy agencies; global development institutes. A number of socio-technical transformations have radically changed the research landscapes in the past decade. The inexorable transformation of different aspects of reality into quantified data has significantly impacted research in several fields, including the many fields linked to sustainability studies.

This process of *datafication* (Kitchin, 2022; van Dijk, 2014) presents unprecedented opportunities for researchers, enabling the collection of data at a scale, granularity and temporality unimaginable until recently. This enhances researchers' ability to monitor, understand, model and predict complex systems involved in the study of sustainability transition - such as ecological, economic and social systems. However, this condition of data abundance comes with important shortcomings and potential pitfalls (boyd and Crawford 2012). The sheer volume of big data requires the adaptation of development of sophisticated and often resource-expensive methods and procedures. The quality of data becomes an issue of concern because data repurposed from non-conventional sources often do not obey established methodological principles such as representativeness and coherence. Moreover, new ethical considerations around privacy, ownership and security arise around data generally not generated for research purposes.

The purpose of this part of the report is to provide insights into what type of innovative sources of data can be adopted in order to study the many dimensions of sustainability transition. Defining innovation is a complex task, as novelty is a contextual and relational property. It has a temporal dimension, related to an element of recency, as well as a domain-specific dimension, in that what is innovative in a certain context is not innovative in another. This general consideration is exacerbated in the case of methodological innovation within academic research because of the proliferation of academic fields, each characterised by different methodological approaches and trajectories. Due to its marked interdisciplinarity and wickedness, sustainability as a phenomenon complicates the picture even further.

Most existing contributions to the issue of methodological innovation in relation to sustainability are strictly linked to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) framework (UN, 2015). In line with the approach outlined in SPES's D2.1 (Biggeri et al., 2023), this report builds upon a different framework revolving around 5 pillars: Productivity; Equity; Environmental Sustainability; Participation & Empowerment; Human Security,

In order to answer the question 'What innovative data are currently leveraged to study the many dimensions of sustainability?', this report adopted a systematic approach, mapping data sources claimed to be innovative within a large sample of academic sources, collected following an expansive operationalisation of the concept of sustainability and leveraging Large Language Models (LLM) for the purpose. It is important to stress that, despite dealing with literature and despite its systematic character, this is by no means a systematic literature review on the topic of innovation in sustainability research, and these results should be taken as indications. The many studies

included in our 'fishnet' are used here as entry-points to extract and classify different types of innovative data sources, and to provide an extensive list of illustrations on the issue. The concrete method adopted, that could be considered innovative in itself, is outlined in the following section.

2. Methods

This part of the report is itself an instructive example of the potential and the limitations associated with innovative approaches to data. Academic texts are in themselves a rather traditional secondary source of information. The rise of academic search engines that allows to retrieve a quasi-exhaustive set of literature sources associated with a list of keywords opened up the way for systematic literature reviews, aimed at mapping a certain domain of knowledge as extensively as possible. Moreover, the steady advancement in Natural Language Processing witnessed in the past decade, which recently scale-jumped with the popularisation of Large Language Models (LLMs), allows to transform a large collection of academic texts into a dataset for quali-quantitative analysis.

The main objective of the literature collected is to generate a substantial amount of data sources to be classified and inspected for illustrative purposes. In order to identify a sample of innovative data sources, the present research adopted a pragmatic approach based on two principles: temporal delimitation and researchers' self-definition. First, we used 2019 as a cut-off point to provide a lower bound to our literature search; the year was chosen because it corresponds to the publication of the report conducted by the MAKSWELL project (Van den Brakel, 2019), a Horizon2020-funded research project that elaborated upon the promises and limitations of non-traditional data sources for the assessment of the SDGs. The assumption behind this choice is that, given the highly dynamic character of methodological innovation, it is more useful to focus on the years following this report. Second, in order to identify literature dealing with innovative data sources, we used the researchers' own claims of novelty contained within the texts. Consequently, we searched for texts containing keywords related to the innovative and novel character of the data and measurements adopted. By delegating the definition of what is innovative to the claims made within the texts we collected, we circumvented the otherwise daunting task of assessing the methodological innovativeness of a number of fields of which the authors are not necessarily experts.

A core component of our methodology has been the adoption of LLMs, and OpenAI's GPT more specifically, as a tool to assist in the exploration of a large set of academic texts. This involved information extraction, classification, selection and enrichment tasks. While constituting an exciting source of methodological innovation and exploration, it is important to remark that LLMs are not infallible. Their performance, in particular, is highly dependent on the quality of input data, as well as on effective prompting. Evaluating their performance however can be a daunting task, considering the many intervening factors and the non-deterministic nature of their outcome. The development of reliable (and affordable) research protocols for exploiting the opportunities of LLMs is a current vibrant area of debate and investigation. While pursuing the ambition to automatically map and classify innovative data sources with the assistance of tools such as search engines and LLMs, we encountered a number of obstacles. These limitations included challenges associated to API limitations and costs (e.g., how much text it is possible to process at a time; unpredictability in the

output of non-deterministic systems) as well as assumptions related to homogeneity and standardisation of data entries (e.g., the proportion of PDF available for automated download; the proportion of book-length publications and theses).

The data collection and analysis followed a number of phases. First, we needed to design an appropriate set of queries that would allow us to collect a large corpus of texts related to innovative data sources used to study different dimensions of sustainability. Second, we relied on GPT to extract specific snippets from the texts, corresponding to the data sources used and related information. Third, we relied on existing reviews to create a classification scheme. Fourth, we instructed a model to automatically classify each data source into a data category. Fifth, we compiled a list of examples that illustrates how different categories of data sources have been used by recent studies to investigate the different dimensions of sustainability.

2.1. Designing the query

Our queries resulted from the combination of two components: a variable theme-specific component, and a fixed innovation-related component.

The fixed innovation-related component of the query is composed of different formulations aimed at distinguishing established from new types of data sources. This consisted in including a wide series of fixed phrases and combinations of literal keywords formatted in a series of OR logical statements:

"novel data source" OR "new data source" OR "innovative data source" OR "nonconventional data source" OR "non-conventional data source" OR "novel source of data" OR "new source of data" OR "innovative source of data" OR "nonconventional source of data" OR "non-conventional source of data" OR "novel data sources" OR "new data sources" OR "innovative data sources" OR "nonconventional data sources" OR "non-conventional data sources" OR "novel sources of data" OR "new sources of data" OR "innovative sources of data" OR "nonconventional sources of data" OR "non-conventional sources of data" OR "novel measure" OR "new measure" OR "innovative measure" OR "nonconventional measure" OR "non conventional measure" OR "novel measure" OR "novel measures" OR "new measures" OR "innovative measures" OR "nonconventional measures" OR "non conventional measures" OR "novel measures" OR "novel measurement" OR "new measurement" OR "innovative measurement" OR "nonconventional measurement" OR "non-conventional measurement" OR "novel measurement" OR "novel measurements" OR "new measurements" OR "innovative measurements" OR "nonconventional measurements" OR "non-conventional measurements" OR "novel measurements"

The theme specific components emerged from a conceptual exercise in which the goal was to map a sufficient number of dimensions of sustainability, relevant to the project. The starting point for designing this component of the query were the above-mentioned 'five pillars' that constitute the main reference of SPES's theoretical framework. As a pre-emptive measure to address the semantic

overlap between the pillars, we introduced a cross-pillar element taking the epistemological status of a pillar itself, in our querying. This ensured that important dimensions of economy, energy, research and innovation were not left unaddressed seeing as they are a part of a more intersectional dimension.

Each pillar represents a broad, albeit essential component of sustainability. For this reason, for each pillar we agreed upon three dimensions that best represent areas of investigation relevant for the SPES project. The name of the pillar itself has also been included together with these additional three dimensions per pillar. Each dimension has been further decomposed into three more specific sub-dimensions, each associated to one or more keywords to account for lexical, orthographic or stylistic variations. These keywords (88 in total) represented the theme-specific component of our queries (see Figure 1). It is important to stress that neither the relation between pillars and dimensions nor the relation between dimensions and phenomena is to be understood in terms of exhaustiveness. As already explained, the scope of this literature search was extensive rather than exhaustive. Nonetheless, grounding our literature search on this hierarchical unfolding of the concept of sustainability allowed us to craft an effective 'fishnet' that ensured to cover a broad and diverse semantic field.

Figure 1: Hierarchical Operationalisation of Pillars, Dimensions and Keywords

Our queries resulted from the combination of the 88 theme-specific component and the innovation-related component with an AND operator, hence resulting in a total of 88 queries. Before proceeding with launching the queries and collecting the resulting literature sources, we manually tested several queries and evaluated their results for relevance.

Another important operative choice taken in the querying process: that of adopting a literal search approach in Google Scholar, by enclosing the search terms into double quotes. This implies that any text that does not literally match the necessarily specific formulation of our query is not included in our corpus. Such operative choice is likely to have left out relevant literature sources, but it was deemed necessary after realising that a semantic search (i.e., a search that attempts to match the contextual meaning of a query) was generating too many false positives. Since our goal, as mentioned, was not that of producing an accurate representation of methodological innovation, but rather to generate as many useful examples as possible, false positives are more of a problem than false negatives.

2.2. Collecting a corpus of texts

For simplicity, we decided to use Google Scholar as a search engine, since it is widely used by the scholarly community and its logic allowed us to easily scale query execution. The choice to focus on a single search engine has likely left out some relevant source from our search; however, including other academic search engines (such as Scopus or WebOfScience) would have significantly increased the overall effort, since it would have required developing additional *ad hoc* parsers.

Figure 2: Flowchart of steps taken to collect corpus

The 88 queries reported above have been launched programmatically through a custom script. For each query, we stored the HTML code of the first 5 result pages, each containing up to 10 results (see Figure 2). Hence, we collected up to 50 literature results for each query / keyword, albeit some queries returned less than the maximum. The queries returned a total of 3,732 literature sources, which included a substantial number of duplicates. After deduplicating, we were left with 1,274.

The HTML pages resulting from the Google Scholar queries have been parsed in order to partially automate the literature sources collection. Roughly half of the literature sources retrieved were available in open access and the corresponding entry displayed a direct PDF link. This allowed us to automatically download such entries programmatically. The remaining sources included both non-open access sources, requiring institutional authentication, and open access sources that did not provide a direct PDF link. For these sources we proceeded with manual collection.

Several other factors reduced our sample of literature sources further. This includes filtering obvious false-positives, BA theses and chapters from books that we could not retrieve. Some publications provided unforeseen technical difficulties in relation to formatting or did not include text-elements that allowed us to extract the text from the PDF file. This reduced our number of sources in our corpus from 903 PDF files to a final of 882 text files.

2.3.Extracting information

In order to extract relevant information from the corpus of texts we relied on OpenAI's APIs, through which it is possible to interrogate their Large Language Models (GPT3.5-turbo and GPT4-turbo). We developed a script interrogating OpenAI APIs, tasked to extract from each literature source snippets of text, as literal as possible, related to: each data source mentioned in the text; the phenomenon for which such data has been adopted; the method used to analyse such data; a one-liner elaborating on the use of the data source. Moreover, for each text, the model also extracted a number of metadata: authors; year of publication; title; journal; field; a brief summary.

After comparing the outcome of both GPT4-turbo and GPT3.5-turbo, we concluded that they performed very similarly on our extraction tasks, hence we opted for the more cost-effective GPT3.5-turbo. This however comes with an important limitation related to the necessity to process smaller chunks of text, since this model has a smaller maximum length of text that it can process. Consequently, we restricted each query to the model to 13,000 characters of text. In order to minimise the risk that the section of the text mentioning data and methods would be excluded from the analysis, while keeping costs and time for data collection under control, we decided to limit the information extraction to the two first chunks of 13,000 characters from each text. It is necessary to mention that a certain amount of texts consisted of entire books / theses, hence the chunking might have left important aspects of these sources out of the scope of the analysis.

The extraction task resulted in 2,945 entries, corresponding to each individual combination of data sources, phenomena and methods identified by the model within the texts.

2.4. Creating a classification scheme

For the creation of a classification scheme, we also relied on GPT. In this case, we adopted the dialogue version ChatGPT, and more in particular we created a CustomGPT (based on the most performant GPT4), which is a version of ChatGPT that is tailored to a specific task and topic through a customisation of the background knowledge that the model builds upon in order to provide its answers. We trained our CustomGPT with recent publications on the topic of innovative and non-traditional data for the study of sustainability collected through a cursory literature search (Del Río Castro et al., 2021; Del Vecchio et al., 2018; ElMassah & Mohieldin, 2020; Fritz et al., 2019; Ilieva & McPhearson, 2018; Kharrazi et al., 2016; van den Brakel et al., 2019; Weber et al., 2021).

Initial attempts to generate a purely inductive classification scheme, one emerging from the bottom-up based on the list of data sources extracted by the model, did not yield satisfactory results. Consequently, we relied on the texts that we included in the CustomGPT, and asked the model to consolidate the type of data sources mentioned as innovative in these texts into a codebook, that in turn could be used to classify an extensive list of data sources. After a few iterations, we settled for the following coding scheme:

1. *Social Media Data*: User-generated data from social media platforms which can be analysed for trends, public opinion, and behaviour related to sustainability (e.g., Twitter feeds on environmental issues, Instagram posts on recycling practices)
2. *Citizen Science Data*: Data collected by the general public through participation in scientific research (e.g., Environmental monitoring, biodiversity tracking, community-led surveys)
3. *Urban Big Data*: Large volumes of data generated within urban settings, public transportation systems, urban sensors, etc. (e.g., Traffic flow data, public transportation data, urban infrastructure usage)
4. *Remote Sensing and Satellite Data*: Data collected via satellites and aerial imaging, useful for monitoring environmental changes, land use, and urban development (e.g., Deforestation tracking, urban heat islands, coastline changes)
5. *Mobile Phone and Telecommunication Data*: Data generated from mobile phone usage and telecommunication networks, useful for understanding human mobility and communication patterns (e.g., Movement patterns during natural disasters, communication trends in response to public awareness campaigns)
6. *Internet of Things Data*: Data from interconnected devices and sensors, often used for monitoring and optimising resource use (e.g., Smart energy metres, water quality sensors in rivers and lakes)
7. *Administrative and Governmental Data*: Data collected by government bodies and agencies, often as part of their administrative functions (e.g., Census data, municipal waste management records, public transport usage statistics)

8. *Financial Transaction Data*: Data related to economic activities, including transactions, investments, and consumption patterns (e.g., spending patterns on sustainable goods, investment trends in green technologies)
9. *Crowdsourced Data*: Data collected through voluntary contributions from a large number of people, typically via the internet (e.g., crowdsourced environmental monitoring, community reporting platforms)
10. *Web Data*: Data collected from the world wide web, either available for download or obtained through HTML scraping. (e.g., sustainable companies websites, open data repositories on climate data, blogs on social justice activism.)
11. *Other*: Data that does not fit the descriptions of codes from 1 to 10.

2.5. Classifying information

For the classification task, we also relied on OpenAI API's and GPT3.5-turbo model. We followed a few-shot approach, one where the model is trained on a small number of examples - those provided with the codebook. Since LLMs perform inherently better on smaller chunks of text, provided that the instructions are sufficiently clear, we queried OpenAI API for each extracted data source individually. Previous attempts at classifying the entire list of data sources at once through ChatGPT's interface with GPT4, indeed, provided unsatisfactory results. In particular, the model tended to focus mostly on the head and tail of the list, hence incorrectly classifying as 'Other' a substantial number of entries in the central part of the list, even for cases where the classification task seemed very straightforward.

The inclusion of the residual code 'Other' as an explicitly provided classification option turned out to be a critical decision. We ran the classification with both versions of the codebook, including or excluding the option to classify poorly fitting content as 'Other'. Running the classification that included 'Other' as an explicit code resulted in a substantial number of entries being classified as 'Other' (1,291), as well as a few entries being classified with codes not included in the codebook (69). A cursory inspection of the entries classified as 'Other' confirmed the low incidence of false negatives in the classification task (i.e., entries that should have been classified with other codes), and made it clear that their high number was largely due to some of the literature sources being a weak match to our search criteria (e.g., the adoption of the keywords 'novel' and 'new' in relation to recency and not to novelty; the query matching the reference list rather than the body of the text). This confirmed that the coding scheme including the category 'Other' was a better choice than the one which did not, since it would have included a large proportion of false positives (i.e., entries that should have not been classified with a certain code). An inspection of a sample of the classified entries confirmed the low incidence of such false positives, which would have significantly altered the distributions of data categories and would have constituted an important source of noise for the selection of illustrative examples.

2.6. Selecting illustrative examples

We developed a dataset comprising 1,585 entries, each representing a data source identified as innovative in academic texts. These sources were categorised based on their use in studying various dimensions of sustainability. To illustrate the diversity of these data sources, we organised examples according to the dimensions that we used to operationalise sustainability, according to the pillars laid out by Biggeri et al. (2023) in the SPES framework. For each sustainability dimension, we selected one example publication, corresponding to one of the three most frequently occurring data categories within that dimension. Given that each combination of dimension and data category could consist of several dozen entries, we employed GPT to assist in making an informed selection of the most innovative and informative examples for each combination of data category and sustainability dimension. This process involved iterating over the 23 identified dimensions of sustainability and the top three data categories within each. We prompted the GPT API to extract what it deemed the most innovative example in each case. Initially, our classified dataset was based solely on excerpts that included the data source, the studied phenomenon, the methodology, and an overview of the use of sources. However, we found that the resulting list of examples lacked the depth and detail necessary for our purposes. To address this, we enriched and refined each example using ChatGPT. We input the entire text corresponding to each example into the model and prompted it to elaborate on how the data source was used innovatively to study the specific phenomenon. This step provided the necessary polish to our examples, making them more suitable for demonstrating innovative uses of data sources in sustainability research. Each extracted elaboration was subsequently reviewed and adjusted for accuracy.

3. Results

3.1. Overview of data categories

The following table (Table 1) lists the occurrences of data sources for each data category included in the classification scheme. The count of data sources per each data source provides an overview of the distribution. The data categories are additionally utilised to differentiate and structure the illustrative examples provided in the subsequent section.

Data Categories	Count
Administrative and Governmental Data	362
Social Media Data	288
Remote Sensing and Satellite Data	248
Financial Transaction Data	131
Citizen Science Data	122
Web Data	120
Urban Big Data	115
Internet of Things Data	82
Mobile Phone and Telecommunication Data	77
Crowdsourced Data	40

Table 1: Count of Data Sources across Data Categories

The following network graph (Figure 3) summarises the relation patterns between data categories (in blue) and the sustainability pillars (in green), based on which study used which type of data. The connections (links) between a data category and a sustainability pillar are based on the frequency with which data sources within that category have been used to study phenomena related to the respective pillar. Essentially, the graph visualises which types of data are most commonly employed in research pertaining to each pillar of sustainability.

Figure 3: Network graph of relational patterns between data categories and sustainability pillars

Administrative and government data is relied upon within the pillars of equity, productivity and security, while Remote Sensing and Satellite data are strongly tied to the environmental pillar. Social media data is relied comparatively more upon within the pillars of empowerment, environment and security. Citizen Science data is strongly connected with the environmental pillar. Crowdsourced data is generally linked with the security pillar.

The following heatmap (Figure 4) plots the co-occurrences of the data categories and dimensions of sustainability. The darker the colour of the cell, the more often a data source classified within a certain category has been employed to study the corresponding dimension.

Figure 4: Heatmap of co-occurrence of data categories and dimensions of sustainability

Within our innovative corpus, Administrative and Governmental data have been mostly used to study the labour market, welfare and the judicial system. Social Media data are framed as particularly useful to study climate change, collective action and social cohesion. Financial Transactions data are closely tied to studies of economic growth and poverty. Remote Sensing and Satellite data are used to study predominantly sustainability dimensions such as environment, climate change, biodiversity and pollution. Citizen Science data is generally used to study biodiversity, welfare and poverty.

3.2. Illustrative examples

The goal of this section is to provide a list of examples that illustrate how different types of innovative data sources are used to study several dimensions of sustainability. This section is intended as a navigational map that can be traversed by the reader according to their own domain-specific research interests. The examples are organised by dimension, and each is grouped according to the corresponding pillar. For each dimension, each example illustrates one of the three

most frequently adopted categories of data. Table 2 is offered as a readers-guide, providing an overview of the illustrative examples¹.

Within the pillar of environmental sustainability, the chosen studies utilise remote sensing and satellite data (Guo et al., 2020), big data from urban infrastructures (Chaudhuri & Bose, 2020), and social media data (Mouttaki et al., 2022) to address challenges in land cover accuracy, disaster management, and ecosystem services mapping. These approaches exemplify the potential of combining high-resolution images, field surveys, and deep learning models to enhance accuracy and efficiency in environmental analysis.

For the productivity-pillar, the chosen studies have used remote sensing for crop yield forecasting (Yli-Heikkilä et al., 2021), administrative data for studying the impact of innovation on firm performance (Bedford et al., 2021), and web data for analysing economic patterns (Zhang et al., 2022). These publications emphasise the potential of integrating various data sources, including Earth Observation data and financial transaction data, to develop more nuanced and comprehensive analytical models.

Relating to the pillar of equity, the chosen publications employ financial transaction data to explore wealth inequality (Waltl, 2020) and crowdsourced narratives to understand the experiences of older adults during the pandemic (Kyröläinen et al., 2022). These innovative approaches demonstrate the use of detailed transaction records and linguistic analysis to gain deeper insights into social issues.

The pillar of empowerment is addressed through the analysis of social media data (Al Tamime et al., 2022), urban big data for traffic patterns (Rahman et al., 2021), and governmental data for political survey inferences (Ghitza & Gelman, 2020). These studies illustrate the potentials of utilising large-scale datasets and advanced algorithms for enhancing understanding in fields such as gender disparities and democratic engagement.

In research related to the pillar of security, we noted the use of IoT data for real-time traffic safety (Li, 2021) and social media data for mental health community analysis (Tang et al., 2021). These approaches represent opportunities within a potential shift towards more dynamic and comprehensive data utilisation, contributing to fields like traffic management and mental health support.

Finally, cross-pillar studies, such as those analysing start-up firm dynamics (Couture & Houle, 2020) and energy models using IoT data (Happle, 2020), highlight the interdisciplinary nature of contemporary research. These publications demonstrate the effectiveness of combining different data sources, like administrative records and environmental sensors, to create more robust and insightful analyses across various domains.

¹ It is important to disclose that these illustrative examples originate from an extraction assisted by chatGPT, which was reviewed for accuracy and modified accordingly.

Table 2: Map overview of illustrative examples

Section	Pillar	Dimension	Data Category	Data Source
3.2.1	Environment	Environmental sustainability	Remote Sensing and Satellite Data	FROM-GLC30 2017 dataset
		Climate change	Urban Big Data	Images from smart urban infrastructures
		Biodiversity	Social Media Data	Flickr images
		Pollution	Administrative and Governmental Data	GHG Platform India
3.2.2	Productivity	Productivity	Remote Sensing and Satellite Data	Earth Observation data
		Technological Innovation	Administrative and Governmental Data	Intellectual Property Government Open Data
		Economic Growth	Web Data	Online news data
		Labour Market	Social Media Data	LinkedIn Internal Audit Function data
3.2.3	Equity	Equity	Financial Transaction Data	Limited entry permit transactions database
		Poverty	Financial Transaction Data	National accounts and Household Finance Consumption Survey
		Welfare	Crowdsourced Data	Wellness diaries
		Inclusivity	Web Data	Google Trends data
3.2.4	Empowerment	Empowerment	Social Media Data	Online advertising data
		Collective Action	Urban Big Data	Microwave Vehicle Detection System
		Democratic Engagement	Administrative and Governmental Data	Voter Registration Databases
		Social Cohesion	Administrative and Governmental Data	Administrative dataset of civil complaints
3.2.5	Security	Human Security	Crowdsourced Data	Barometer Initiative
		Safety	Internet of Things Data	Connected Vehicles and smartphone sensors
		Solidarity	Social Media Data	Online Depression-Focused Communities data
		Judicial System	Administrative and Governmental Data	Russian criminal court decisions
3.2.6	Cross-pillars	Economy Cross	Administrative and Governmental Data	National Accounts Longitudinal Microdata File
		Energy	Internet of Things Data	Wearable sensors
		Research & Innovation	Internet of Things Data	Wi-Fi signal detector

3.2.1. Environment

Environmental sustainability: *Remote Sensing and Satellite Data* (Guo et al., 2020)

The publication's innovative use of the FROM-GLC30 2017 dataset in studying land cover accuracy at a continental scale lies in several key aspects. Firstly, it utilises a novel method based on watershed sampling units, which is rare in continental-scale studies. This method, more representative than traditional pixel-based methods, offers a new approach to understanding land cover accuracy. Additionally, the study covers a vast area, including the Pan-Third Pole Area, which spans parts of Asia, Europe, and Africa. The use of high-resolution remote sensing images from Google Earth, coupled with field surveys, allows for a comprehensive and accurate assessment of land cover. The study's results, which include detailed analyses of accuracy variations across different regions and land cover types, contribute significantly to the field by providing insights into the spatial variation of land cover accuracy and laying the groundwork for improved applications of global land cover datasets.

Climate change: *Urban Big Data* (Chaudhuri & Bose, 2020)

The publication's use of images from smart urban infrastructures to study disaster-hit environments in Central Mexico (2017 earthquake) is considered innovative for several reasons. Firstly, it identifies a novel source of data, namely images from smart urban infrastructures, which are crucial for effective disaster management decision-making. This approach is innovative as it involves collecting and analysing images from the affected areas, providing a unique and direct perspective of the disaster's impact. Secondly, the study utilises advanced technology in the form of a deep learning convolutional neural network to analyse this unique dataset. This method allows for a more detailed and sophisticated analysis of the images, enhancing the ability to understand and respond to the crisis effectively. The use of TensorFlow for image classification further exemplifies the cutting-edge nature of this research. The findings from this study are significant as they offer a new way of utilising technology for effective disaster response, demonstrating both the effectiveness and technical viability of this approach in crisis scenarios.

Biodiversity: *Social Media Data* (Mouattaki et al., 2022)

The use of Flickr images to study Cultural Ecosystem Services (CES) mapping is innovative because it applies a deep learning model to automate the classification of natural and human elements relevant to CES. Traditional methods of quantifying and mapping CES are complex due to their intangible nature, and manual content analysis of large numbers of photographs is time-consuming. This study utilised a convolutional neural network architecture to analyse over 29,000 photographs from the Lithuanian coast, employing hierarchical clustering to group these photographs. This approach not only accurately categorised the photographs but also saved a significant amount of manual work (approximately 100 km worth). By enabling the analysis of large numbers of digital photographs, this method expands the analytical tools available to researchers, facilitating the quantification and mapping of CES on a large geographic scale. This automated assessment and

mapping technique can potentially inform urban planning and enhance nature reserve management, making it a significant advancement in the field of CES research.

Pollution: *Administrative and Governmental Data* (Dhingra et al., 2019)

The publication's use of GHG Platform India for studying Greenhouse Gas Emission Estimates from the AFOLU (Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use) sector in India at the subnational level is innovative for several reasons. Firstly, the estimates are primarily based on aggregated secondary data collected by the Vasudha Foundation from nationally recognised documents and reports, involving interactions with external experts for inputs on data availability and emission estimation approaches. This approach facilitates a comprehensive and collaborative assessment. Secondly, the study provides time-series emission estimates for the period 2005 to 2015 at the state (sub-national) level, adhering to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National GHG Inventories and other internationally accepted guidance. This level of granularity in data allows for more precise and localised understanding of emission sources and trends. Lastly, the study's findings are publicly available, aiming to enhance discussion, address data gaps, and contribute to policy dialogue on India's GHG emissions profile and related policies. This transparency and commitment to engaging a broader audience in climate change discussions represent a significant step forward in environmental research and policy development.

3.2.2. Productivity

Productivity: *Remote Sensing and Satellite Data* (Yli-Heikkilä et al., 2021)

The publication's innovative use of Earth Observation (EO) data in crop yield forecasting lies in its comprehensive and automated approach, which integrates EO data, administrative data, agrometeorological data, and historical crop statistics. This method streamlines what was previously a labour-intensive process, enabling more efficient and cost-effective forecasting. The system utilises advanced artificial intelligence techniques to provide pre-harvest yield predictions for key cereal crops. Moreover, the implementation of this EO-based forecasting method represents a significant shift towards automated, data-driven agricultural statistics, potentially offering more accurate and timely insights for sustainable agriculture and informed decision-making.

Technological innovation: *Administrative and Governmental Data* (Bedford et al., 2021)

The publication's innovative approach lies in its application of the Intellectual Property Government Open Data 2019 to extend and replicate prior findings on the relationship between innovation, future profitability, and stock returns in the context of Australian firms. This study diverges from previous U.S.-focused research, addressing the unique Australian setting where innovation and patenting activities are less prevalent. By integrating patent data with firm-level financial and market data, it provides new insights into the impact of innovation on firm performance in a different legal and economic environment. This contributes to a more nuanced understanding of how innovation influences profitability and stock market performance in various contexts, offering valuable implications for policymakers and investors in countries with different levels of innovation intensity.

Economic growth: *Web Data* (Zhang et al., 2022)

The publication's innovative use of online news data from Baidu, Jinritoutiao, Fengguangwang, Sina News, Souhu News, and Wangyi News to study spatial-temporal patterns of economic output values in Yinzhou, Ningbo, China, lies in its pioneering approach in a region where this methodology is relatively unexplored. While previous studies have used online news and search engine data to forecast economic patterns and stock market trends, particularly in the U.S., the application of this technique in China, especially for understanding spatial-temporal dynamics, is limited. This study is innovative in its exploration of these patterns and the development of models like Generalized Linear Model (GLM) and Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) to predict economic dynamics using online news data. This approach not only demonstrates the potential of online news in forecasting economic trends in China but also suggests a new dimension to augment traditional surveillance systems with a spatial-temporal perspective, which could be applicable to larger geographical areas.

Labour market: *Social Media Data* (Renschler et al., 2023)

The publication's innovative use of LinkedIn Internal Audit Function (IAF) data from Revelio Labs in studying IAF competency and financial reporting failures is notable for several reasons. Firstly, it introduces a new data source to the IAF literature, transitioning from traditional survey-based data to a more robust and objective dataset. The LinkedIn IAF data, aggregated by Revelio Labs, provides several advantages. It allows for a more objective sample composition, as it does not rely on voluntary participation, and offers more detailed and accurate data collection on individual personnel on a longitudinal basis. This shift enables a more comprehensive understanding of IAF competency and its impact on financial reporting quality, leading to insights that were previously unattainable with survey-based approaches.

3.2.3. Equity

Equity: *Financial Transaction Data* (Ayers & Chan, 2020)

The publication's use of the limited entry permit transactions database to study the ownership of Hawai'i longline fleet limited entry permits is innovative primarily due to its comprehensive and detailed approach. The dataset includes records of 6,171 transactions from 1991 to 2017, encompassing permit transfers, renewals, and changes in permit status. Notably, the study differentiates between 'permit holders' (entities whose names are on the permits) and 'permit applicants' (entities that applied for the permits). This distinction is crucial because it acknowledges the complexity of ownership in this context, where an entity may be an individual vessel owner, a business entity (like an LLC or a corporation), or an agent representing others. The separate analysis of permit holders and applicants allows for a more nuanced understanding of ownership changes and trends in the fleet, which is essential for effective fisheries management and policy-making.

Poverty: *Financial Transaction Data* (Waltl, 2020)

The innovative aspect of using National accounts data and top-tail-adjusted HFCS (Household Finance and Consumption Survey) data to study wealth inequality lies in their ability to create a more accurate and comprehensive view of wealth distribution. This method effectively addresses the limitations of traditional surveys, which often underrepresent the wealthiest individuals. By integrating national accounts data with survey data, and making adjustments for the top tail of the wealth distribution using models like Pareto and Generalized Pareto, the approach offers a more accurate representation of the wealth distribution across different sections of society. This enhanced accuracy is crucial for understanding the true extent and nature of wealth inequality, allowing for more effective policy-making and economic analysis.

Welfare: *Crowdsourced Data* (Kyröläinen et al., 2022)

The use of the CoSoWELL project to study written narratives by North American older adults before and during the pandemic is considered innovative for several reasons. Firstly, it provides a unique corpus of English narratives written by this demographic, capturing their experiences both before and during the pandemic. This corpus is enriched with detailed lexical and syntactic annotations at the word level, along with demographic and psychological participant metadata from the CoSoWELL survey. Secondly, the project's design and initial data collection predate the COVID-19 pandemic, allowing for a broader scope of research beyond just the psychological outcomes of the pandemic. The comprehensive goal of the project is to study changes in language use as a function of age, social isolation, and perceived loneliness, using personal life stories to gain insights into the memory functioning and overall mental and emotional well-being of older adults. This approach is innovative as it combines linguistic analysis with demographic and psychological data to provide a multifaceted understanding of the effects of ageing and social factors on older adults.

Inclusivity: *Web Data* (Boss et al., 2023)

The publication's innovative use of Google Trends to study refugee flows from 150 origin countries to the EU27 lies in its development of monthly refugee flow forecasting models that leverage machine learning and high-dimensional data, including digital trace data from Google Trends, and integrates a wide range of classical predictors capturing socio-economic, labour, and monetary statistics. This approach is particularly innovative because it allows for near real-time availability of data, which is a significant advantage over traditional methods that often suffer from data availability and publishing lags. For instance, the ensemble model, which combines Random Forest and Extreme Gradient Boosting algorithms and is based exclusively on Google Trends variables, consistently outperforms other models for forecasting horizons between 3 to 12 months. Especially in the top-20 corridors with significant refugee flows, this Google Trends Index (GTI)-only specification surpasses all other models, highlighting its potential as a tool for refugee forecasting in large-flow corridors.

3.2.4. Empowerment

Empowerment: *Social Media Data* (Al Tamime et al., 2022)

The publication's innovative approach lies in its utilisation of aggregate anonymous online advertising audience estimates from platforms like Facebook, Google, and LinkedIn. This method provides real-time data on demographic distributions, particularly gender disparities, in the professional domain. Traditional data sources such as surveys or censuses often lack the geographical and temporal resolution, especially in lower-income countries. By leveraging these digital platforms' data, the study offers more immediate and detailed insights into gender inequalities, filling existing data gaps with a novel, real-time, and large-scale data source. This approach is particularly valuable in analysing gender-related aspects of Sustainable Development Goal 5, which focuses on gender equality and women's empowerment.

Collective action: *Urban Big Data* (Rahman et al., 2021)

The publication's use of the Microwave Vehicle Detection System (MVDS) to study hurricane evacuation traffic patterns is considered innovative due to its development of a comprehensive data pipeline that incorporates automated data quality checking, data imputation, and spatiotemporal visualisation of large-scale traffic data. This approach allowed for a detailed understanding of the changes in traffic patterns during Hurricane Irma's evacuation. By collecting MVDS data from four major highways in Florida, which handled the majority of the evacuation traffic, the study provided valuable insights into the network-wide spatiotemporal evacuation traffic patterns. This methodology represents a significant advancement as it leverages large-scale, real-time data, which was previously underutilised, to enhance the understanding of the extent and distribution of evacuation traffic, thereby aiding transportation agencies in better planning and managing such scenarios.

Democratic engagement: *Administrative and Governmental Data* (Ghitza & Gelman, 2020)

The publication's innovative use of Voter Registration Databases (VRDs) for improving inferences from political surveys lies in its ability to leverage large-scale political variables such as party registration and past voting behaviour, which are free of overreporting bias or endogeneity between survey responses. The developed process utilises multilevel regression and poststratification to produce vote choice estimates for the presidential election, projecting these estimates to millions of registered voters in a post-election context. This approach results in stable and reasonable inferences across demographic subgroups and small geographic areas, down to the county or congressional district level. This methodology addresses the limitations of traditional exit polls and enhances the precision and reliability of political survey inferences.

Social cohesion: *Administrative and Governmental Data* (Wang & Liu, 2022)

The publication's innovative aspect lies in its comprehensive analysis of parking issues in Brisbane, Australia, using a large-scale administrative dataset of civil complaints. This approach provides a unique, real-world perspective on parking problems, differing from traditional studies that often rely

on smaller-scale surveys or theoretical models, with the use of spatial regression modelling. By examining spatial and temporal patterns of parking complaints in both inner and outer city areas, the study offers a nuanced understanding of how parking issues vary across different urban settings and times, emphasising the need for sustainable mobility and liveability in suburban neighbourhoods. This data-driven approach enables a more targeted and effective policy response, considering the distinct needs of various urban areas and contributing to sustainable urban planning.

3.2.5. Security

Human security: *Crowdsourced Data* (Paladini & Molloy, 2019)

The publication's use of the Barometer Initiative in Colombia to study inclusive monitoring mechanisms in the implementation of the peace process is innovative due to its approach to more inclusive monitoring. It emphasises the opening up of peace process implementation to a broader range of actors, including those who were previously marginalised. This inclusivity is crucial as it deals with the transformation of commitments into norms, institutions, policies, and actions, addressing the challenges of implementation in a complex, evolving political and social landscape. The Barometer Initiative thereby contributes to a more sustainable and participatory peace process by ensuring diverse voices and concerns are incorporated and addressed throughout the implementation phase.

Safety: *Internet of Things Data* (Li, 2021)

The publication's innovative approach in the realm of real-time traffic safety studies lies in its integration of Connected Vehicles (CV) and mobile sensing techniques. This approach represents a significant shift from traditional methods that relied heavily on infrastructure-based data, limited by fixed-location devices and prone to environmental influences. By leveraging vehicle-based data through CV and mobile sensors, the study offers a more dynamic and comprehensive analysis of traffic conditions. Key innovations include using smartphone sensors for detecting vehicle manoeuvres, semi-supervised learning algorithms to utilise massive unlabelled data efficiently, and real-time crash likelihood prediction models based on CV emulated data. Additionally, the research introduces novel surrogate safety measures for pedestrian and bicycle safety analysis and employs data fusion techniques to enhance model accuracy, illustrating the potential of these technologies in proactive traffic management and safety applications.

Solidarity: *Social Media Data* (Tang et al., 2021)

The publication's innovative approach lies in its comparative analysis of user behaviours in managed and unmanaged Online Depression-Focused Communities (ODCs) in China. Utilising deep learning for text classification and econometrics for behavioural analysis, it offers novel insights into how community management styles impact user participation and support provision. This research enhances the understanding of ODC user dynamics and aids in designing and managing these communities more effectively, potentially improving support for individuals with depression. This

approach is particularly innovative as it bridges the gap in understanding the differences in user behaviour between different types of ODCs, which was previously underexplored.

Judicial system: *Administrative and Governmental Data* (Kudryavtsev, 2021)

The publication's innovative approach lies in its use of an extensive dataset from Russian criminal court decisions between 2009 and 2012 to analyse the link between homicides and holidays. This study diverges from previous research, primarily US-focused, by examining this phenomenon in Russia, thus offering external validity. It challenges the 'broken promises theory,' which suggests marginalised individuals show greater violence during holidays. Surprisingly, the research finds that well-integrated individuals (employed, first-time offenders) display a higher propensity for homicide during holidays than marginalised groups, contradicting existing theories and sparking new discussions on the nature of holiday-related violence.

3.2.6. Cross-pillars

Economy cross: *Administrative and Governmental Data* (Couture & Houle, 2020)

The use of the National Accounts Longitudinal Microdata File (NALMF) in this study to analyse Canadian start-up firms from 2005 to 2013 is considered innovative due to its comprehensive and longitudinal approach. This dataset, created by linking various administrative data sources, allowed for a detailed analysis of start-up firms over time, focusing on aspects like survival rates, gender of ownership, and labour productivity. The study's ability to track cohorts of new firms over an extended period and across different industries provided unique insights into the dynamics and performance of start-up firms in Canada, particularly highlighting differences based on the gender of ownership. This approach is noteworthy for its depth and breadth of analysis, providing a richer understanding of the start-up landscape in Canada.

Energy: *Internet of Things Data* (Happle, 2020)

The publication's innovation in using wearable Internet of Things (IoT) sensors in Singapore for studying occupant presence and behaviour in urban building energy models lies in its novel approach to collecting and analysing large-scale, real-time environmental data. This approach significantly advances the field of Urban Building Energy Models (UBEM) by providing detailed insights into occupant behaviour and environmental exposure. The use of wearable IoT sensors allows for the gathering of granular data on air-conditioning exposure and other environmental factors, which are crucial for creating accurate and diverse occupant behaviour models. This data-driven method enables more precise simulations of energy demand and supply on an urban scale, leading to better-informed decisions for urban planning and energy system design. This approach contrasts with traditional methods that often rely on standardised, less specific assumptions, highlighting its innovative contribution to the field.

Research & innovation: *Internet of Things Data* (Ding et al., 2019)

The publication presents an innovative approach to traffic state monitoring using Wi-Fi signal data, a novel data source in this context. The system is distinguished by its use of an Internet of Things (IoT)-based Wi-Fi signal detector, which is solar-powered and collects Wi-Fi signal data. A filtration and mining algorithm extracts traffic state information, such as travel time, traffic volume, and speed, from the data. This method was tested in a practical field test on a major corridor in China. The results, compared with traditional loop data, showed a high correlation and accuracy in traffic speed and volume estimation. The system's distinctiveness lies in its sustainable, cost-effective deployment, and its ability to provide real-time traffic state monitoring with a novel data source, positioning it as a supplementary tool to traditional traffic monitoring systems.

4. Conclusive remarks

This part of the report presented a mapping of innovative data sources used in various disciplines for the study of sustainability. The research process relied on Large Language Models to enable the distant reading of a large corpus of academic texts. These academic texts have been collected based on an expansive operationalisation of the concept of sustainability. The data sources mentioned in the texts have been extracted and classified according to a coding scheme and served as basis to present illustrative examples.

Our results show that different types of data sources have been claimed as innovative in relation to the different pillars of sustainability, as outlined in the SPES framework (Biggeri et al., 2023). In many cases, methodological innovation derives from identifying sources of data previously unavailable, generated as a by-product of other activities or with other goals in mind than sustainability research. However, novelty is also associated to the innovative use or re-combination of existing data sources, as well as from the integration of different types of data, as testified by the relative prevalence of Administrative and Governmental Data and by the several studies integrating different types of data. These considerations raise two important methodological issues. First, data originally developed for engineering or marketing goals, and only secondarily repurposed for research, come with important issues of representativity, validity and reliability. Second, combining data of different types from heterogeneous sources poses a challenge of integration and harmonisation. For this reason, the second part of the report will focus on methods for data integration and harmonisation.

This report has been based on exploratory research that, despite its limitations, yields great potential for mapping methodological innovation in a field such as sustainability studies. Traditional literature review techniques fall short in capturing the multi-dimensional and inter-disciplinary character of sustainability. Inspired by the procedure laid out in this report, future research can cope with some of its limitations and expand its scope. For example, using more specialised Large Language Models would allow to take advantage of broader context windows. Moreover, it would have great value not to limit the analysis to data, but to include methods of analysis in the scope of the mapping.

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Appendix

This section provides an illustration of the workflow, presenting an overview of the input given to the model and the output returned.

Information extraction

Prompt passed with "system" role:

"0) You are a research assistant.

1) You will get as input the text of an academic article which reference, among other things, data sources.

2) You will identify a list of data sources that the text claims to be innovative.

3) For each innovative data source, you will be asked to extract three types of information: the data source itself; the phenomenon that the data source is used to study; the method used to analyse the data; an explanation of how data are used innovatively. And some additional metadata.

4) The types of information are related to each other: the data sources are used to analyse some phenomena based on a certain method of analysis.

5) For each type of information, you will be asked to provide a literal description, extracted from the text.

6) If you do not find any of the information, please store an N/A value in the same data structure. Always keep the data structure consistent.

7) Collect also the metadata.

8) You will not make up any information."

Prompt passed with "user" role:

[chunk of 13,000 characters from a specific text]

Function's fields description:

```
{
  "data_source": {"type": "string", "description": " Literal description of the data mentioned in this text"},
  "phenomenon": {"type": "string", "description": "Literal description of the phenomenon that is analysed by the related data},
  "method": {"type": "string", "description": "Literal description of the method of analysis used on the related data"},
  "how_innovative": {"type": "string", "description": "A short paragraph describing how data are innovative or how they are used innovatively"}}

```

Output:

```
{
  "data_source": "online job advertisements",
  "phenomenon": "skill needs in knowledge production and transfer occupations",
  "method": "analysis of data from online job advertisements and from the European Skills and Jobs Survey",
  "how_innovative": "The analysis of data from online job advertisements and the European Skills and Jobs Survey provides a comprehensive picture of skills needed in occupations related to science, technology, and ICT, as well as teaching positions from higher education in Europe."}

```

Data source classification

Prompt passed with "system" role:

1. ◦ Code: Citizen Science Data

◦ Description: Data collected by the general public through participation in scientific research.

◦ Examples: Environmental monitoring, biodiversity tracking, community-led surveys.

2. ◦ Code: Urban Big Data
 - Description: Large volumes of data generated within urban settings, public transportation systems, urban sensors, etc.
 - Examples: Traffic flow data, public transportation data, urban infrastructure usage.
3. ◦ Code: Social Media Data
 - Description: User-generated data from social media platforms which can be analysed for trends, public opinion, and behaviour related to sustainability.
 - Examples: Twitter feeds on environmental issues, Instagram posts on recycling practices.
4. ◦ Code: Remote Sensing and Satellite Data
 - Description: Data collected via satellites and aerial imaging, useful for monitoring environmental changes, land use, and urban development.
 - Examples: Deforestation tracking, urban heat islands, coastline changes.
5. ◦ Code: Mobile Phone and Telecommunication Data
 - Description: Data generated from mobile phone usage and telecommunication networks, useful for understanding human mobility and communication patterns.
 - Examples: Movement patterns during natural disasters, communication trends in response to public awareness campaigns.
6. ◦ Code: Internet of Things Data
 - Description: Data from interconnected devices and sensors, often used for monitoring and optimising resource use.
 - Examples: Smart energy metres, water quality sensors in rivers and lakes.
7. ◦ Code: Administrative and Governmental Data
 - Description: Data collected by government bodies and agencies, often as part of their administrative functions.
 - Examples: Census data, municipal waste management records, public transport usage statistics.
8. ◦ Code: Financial Transaction Data
 - Description: Data related to economic activities, including transactions, investments, and consumption patterns.
 - Examples: Spending patterns on sustainable goods, investment trends in green technologies.
9. ◦ Code: Crowdsourced Data
 - Description: Data collected through voluntary contributions from a large number of people, typically via the internet.
 - Examples: Crowdsourced environmental monitoring, community reporting platforms.
10. ◦ Code: Web data
 - Description: Data collected from the world wide web, either available for download or obtained through HTML scraping.
 - Examples: Sustainable companies websites, open data repositories on climate data, blogs on social justice activism.
11. ◦ Code: Other
 - Description: Data that do not fit the descriptions of codes from 1 to 10."

Prompt passed with "user" role:

"Classify the following record according to the code book.

```
{
  "data_source": "online job advertisements",
  "phenomenon": "skill needs in knowledge production and transfer occupations",
  "method": "analysis of data from online job advertisements and from the European Skills and Jobs Survey",
  "how_innovative": "The analysis of data from online job advertisements and the European Skills and Jobs Survey provides a comprehensive picture of skills needed in occupations related to science, technology, and ICT, as well as teaching positions from higher education in Europe."
}
```

Output:

```
{
  "data_category": "Web data"
}
```

Example selection

Prompt passed with “system” role:

In this prompt you will receive a list of records. Each record describe a data source that a certain text described as innovative in the study of a phenomena based on certain methods.

Compare all the records, and select the one that, according to all the information provided, is the most innovative and the most informative.

Most innovative here means that it uses a non-conventional data source (such as data that are not generated for research but that are creatively repurposed for research); or that it uses it in a original way (such as combining different type of data).

Most informative here means that the record contains enough information to assess such innovativeness.

As output, give me the selected record maintaining its exact structure.

Prompt passed with “user” role:

[list of records associated to a combination of data category / dimension]

Example refinement

Human agent

[Attaching PDF of article by Ghitza & Gelman (2020)]

You are a good research assistant who responds only in a single paragraph.

How is this publication's use of Voter Registration Databases to study

Improving inferences from political surveys considered innovative?

You may ONLY respond with a single paragraph.

ChatGPT4

The publication's innovative use of Voter Registration Databases (VRDs) for improving inferences from political surveys lies in its ability to leverage large-scale political variables such as party registration and past voting behavior, which are free of overreporting bias or endogeneity between survey responses. The developed process utilizes multilevel regression and poststratification to produce vote choice estimates for the presidential election, projecting these estimates to millions of registered voters in a post-election context. This approach results in stable and reasonable inferences across demographic subgroups and small geographic areas, down to the county or congressional district level. This methodology addresses the limitations of traditional exit polls and enhances the precision and reliability of political survey inferences.

Part II

Integrating traditional and innovative data sources

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1. Introduction

Since the 1950s, a substantial portion of the statistical information generated by national statistical agencies has originated from sample surveys. Since they were established, sample surveys have been serving as the primary means to acquire reliable, accurate, and regularly updated information regarding the national population and businesses. Beyond describing the world, the data derived from these surveys have been serving various purposes, including informing policy decisions related to economics, social issues, and health. Additionally, they have been contributing to the assessment of the impacts, monitoring the overall health and economic conditions of the population, guiding decisionmaking for businesses and individuals, and fostering extensive research in economics, health, and social domains.

However, in recent years, surveys have encountered several challenges, including diminishing response rates, escalating costs, and a growing demand from users for more timely and granular data and statistics. The wealth of information is far from being threatened though. Nowadays, there has been a surge in data from alternative sources, such as administrative records generated by government agencies, satellite and sensor data, private-sector information like electronic health records and credit card transactions, and massive datasets accessible on the internet.

Novelties often come with questions: How can these emerging data sources be effectively utilised to complement or even substitute some of the information traditionally collected through surveys? How can they pave the way for new possibilities in generating information and statistics that contribute to the improvement of society?

The use of alternative data sources encounters some problems and at the same time affects classical survey programs. For instance, new data sources may lead to changes in measurement, and the existence of innovative data sources needs the development of approaches to link these alternative sources to universal frames to assess representativeness.

The past two decades have seen a profound "data revolution" in the field of social sciences, propelled by technological advancement. This era has provided researchers with access to diverse and extensive datasets in electronic formats. A significant portion of cutting-edge quantitative social science research stems from the creativity of researchers who skilfully integrate disparate datasets collected independently.

The emergence of new data sources, coupled with evolving perspectives, has broadened the scope of data integration and harmonisation, accentuating the need to explore, exploit, and develop statistical techniques in the realm of data integration. This expanding landscape necessitates ongoing research to address the complexities inherent in this dynamic field. Leveraging multiple data sources holds the potential to enhance the production of official statistics and advance research. The long tradition in the integration of survey data, such as EU-SILC, with national administrative data (income data registers, students registers; see, e.g., Jantti et al., 2013) is an example of how combining different data sources may allow the measurement and monitoring of social mobility, inter-generational inequality, and poverty. There are many other examples of opportunities given by the integration of different sources. For instance, if one is interested in

analysing enterprises and their innovation and sustainable practices, one can integrate traditional sources, such as the national enterprises' census or ad hoc surveys, with information from web scraping data where text analysis is performed to the text on their website (see, e.g., Van der Doef et al., 2018; van den Brakel et al., 2019). When a probability survey is available for the target population of enterprises (e.g., a survey on start-ups), one can use methods to combine this information with the data arising from web scraping to make inferences about the determinants of innovation for this company. For a final example, we move to the dimension of environmental sustainability. The extensive availability of satellite imagery allows granularity and timeliness of data production on, e.g., land use (see, e.g., the [CLMS project](#)³). At the same time, the collection of daily pollution data via sensors is well established (see, e.g., the [CAMS project](#)⁴). Leveraging surveys at the municipal level, collecting - among other things - information on urban green areas, waste production, presence and activity of waste-disposal plants (among others, see [the Italian urban environmental data survey](#)), one could construct reliable and representative environmental indicators (UNOOSA, 2018). For further examples of the use of satellite imagery and remote sensing data, see Paganini et al. (2018); Anderson et al. (2017); Donaldson and Storeygard (2016). Yet, the integration of information from diverse sources requires meticulous attention, demanding a profound understanding of the distinctive properties inherent in each dataset and the statistical outcomes that arise from their harmonisation.

This part of the report aims to provide an overview for a broader audience of the statistical methods developed in the last decades in Official statistics and Survey statistics to deal with data integration issues. This part of the report is structured as follows. Section 1 concerns data integration as methods to create a synthetic dataset merging information from different sources. Section 2 deals with the issue of combining probability and nonprobability samples for inference. Section 3 is a collection of blue boxes that supply available statistical software. The reader can find other kinds of boxes throughout the text: the green ones propose toy/practical examples to exemplify both the issues at stake and the yellow ones provide statistical details of the suggested methods. Finally, the Appendix includes a flowchart supporting the users in the choice of the most suitable methods according to their needs.

1. Creation of a synthetic dataset

In this section, we present two data integration procedures, namely, record linkage and statistical matching. Such procedures aim to integrate two (or more) datasets that contain information on a set of common variables and variables that are not jointly observed. As output, the implementation of these integration procedures gives a set of pairs of records.

Although at first glance they could seem almost the same thing, record linkage and statistical matching differ in at least four aspects. The first two aspects concern the aim of the procedures and the nature

³ Copernicus Land Monitoring Service

⁴ Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service

Figure 1: Ranking of creation of synthetic dataset from data-based to model-based methods (reproduced based on Asher et al. (2020))

of the information to integrate. Record linkage mainly aims to identify pairs of records corresponding to a single statistical unit that are present in different databases; statistical matching seeks to derive integrated statistical information by combining information from different datasets in which only some variables are observed twice and the overlapping of observed units is not necessary. Another aspect concerns the fact that, in a record linkage procedure, the common variables are sometimes misreported or subject to change, while statistical matching does not have to deal with the problem of the quality of collected data. Record linkage provides a solution to the problem of the quality of collected data collected introducing the linkage procedure parameters such as the probability of having observed the variable without noise. Finally, the procedures differ in the hypotheses at the base of the methodologies; while record linkage may not introduce any strong assumption on the conditional distribution of the variables of interest, statistical matching mainly works assuming conditional independence.

As portrayed in Figure 1, following the ranking outlined by Asher et al. (2020), first, we have deterministic record linkage which is the most traditional methods that rely on rules-based data integration. It involves simply combining records that share an identical key, such as a unique identifier, or when this is not available, a set of identifiers (referred to as a key) that uniquely identify an individual. Typically, this key is available for most records in one or more datasets. In probabilistic record linkage, a probability model is used to assess the probability that a pair of records represent the same entity. Statistical Matching, instead, is the most model-driven methods that match records with similar characteristics across multiple covariates, allowing for comparisons of values for a different set of variables.

1.1. Record Linkage

Record linkage, known by various terms such as data linkage, record linkage, data matching, entity resolution, deduplication, data matching, and instance matching, is the practice of identifying records in two or more data sources that pertain to the same entity. When the linkage process is precise and reliable, then the information from the sources can be merged, allowing researchers to study relationships among variables measured in the individual sources. The effectiveness of a record linkage method hinges on the extent to which the information available in the two sources can successfully distinguish and link records i.e., individual persons, households, or businesses. Many methods exist for linking records and assessing the quality of the linkages (for a comprehensive view see among others National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (2023), Binette and Steorts (2022), Asher et al. (2020), Reiter (2021)).

Toy Example 1: Creation of a synthetic dataset via Record Linkage

Here is an example of a scenario where we find ourselves with the problem of creating a synthetic dataset. Let us suppose we have two distinct datasets collecting information about sustainability practices and the energy consumption of individuals in Ireland. In this application, we do not care about the design behind the datasets. Only dataset A collects information on individuals' energy consumption, whereas dataset B lists individuals' recycling rates - which are missing in A. Both datasets contain some common variables, namely citizen's name, and residence address.

DATASET A: CITIZEN			
ID	Name	Address	Monthly Energy Consumption
DA.1	Em Green	456 Oak Avenue	500 kWh
DA.2	Alex Smith	789 Pine Street	300 kWh
DA.3	Sarah Johnson	102 Maple Drive	400 kWh
DA.4	Liam Murphy	31 Birch Road	250 kWh

MATCH?

MATCH?

DATASET B: CITIZEN			
ID	Name	Address	Recycling Rate
DB.1	Jessica Miller	123 Maple Lane	95%
DB.2	Sarah Johson	102 Maple Driv	75%
DB.3	Emily Green	456 Oak Ave	80%
DB.4	Michael Rodriguez	23 Elm Street	40%

Our objective is to create a complete synthetic dataset that integrates information from both datasets linking individuals in dataset A with those in B according to the values of the common variables (often called *matching variables*) while accounting for variations in names and addresses. With a very small sample size and in the absence of errors, individuals' names could be considered as unique identifiers. However, on the one hand, it is common to work with large datasets, which implies that it is likely to encounter homonyms, and, on the other hand, measurement errors (e.g., typing errors) are frequent. Hence, when there are no unique identifiers, we are not able to simply match the individuals in the datasets. The challenge lies in accurately linking records with variations in the matching variables.

Record linkage techniques are essential in various fields, including epidemiology, social sciences, and business analytics, as they facilitate accurate identity resolution, leading to more informed decisionmaking and research outcomes. These techniques enable the incorporation of variables measured in additional data sources into the primary data sources. For example, survey records of individuals can be linked to attributes related to the geographic regions in which survey respondents reside or the affiliations and associations to which they belong. Furthermore, when merging two or more datasets, each representing a subset of the population, these techniques enable the expansion of the dataset by increasing the number of records. They also facilitate the construction of longitudinal datasets by establishing connections between records associated with the same individuals over time, such as merging high school records with data on college completion. In a broader context, they offer a means to validate the accuracy of data within a source by cross-referencing it with other sources (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2023).

Figure 2: Reproduced based on (Binette and Steorts, 2022)

The process of linking records is a multi-stage operation that encompasses four distinct phases, with Record Linkage serving as just one of these pivotal stages (see Figure 2). Each of these stages plays a critical role in the overall process, from data preparation to record linkage, ultimately culminating in the successful integration of information from disparate sources. This sequential approach ensures a systematic and comprehensive handling of data, guaranteeing the accuracy and effectiveness of record linkage as an integral component of the broader procedure. In the initial stage, records are meticulously parsed to identify a common set of attributes or fields shared among the dataset. This step lays the foundation for subsequent comparisons. Attribute alignment includes also the standardisation of variables. Similar records are then thoughtfully grouped into 'blocks.' Only records residing within the same block are subjected to direct comparison; records that do not share a block are promptly determined to be non-matches. This technique, often referred to as "blocking" is a crucial strategy aimed at reducing the number of potential candidate pairs that need to be examined. By grouping records based on specific criteria, blocking ensures that only records with shared characteristics are compared, thus effectively managing the scalability of record linkage in large datasets (Christen and Christen, 2012). Blocking, for instance, involves grouping records according to certain criteria, such as comparing records with identical zip or postcode values, which streamlines the linkage process (Asher et al., 2020). However, this approach comes with a caveat - the exact propagation of uncertainty from the blocking phase to the record linkage stage is not always achievable. Consequently, the record linkage task may inherit errors from the blocking stage, some of which may remain unresolved. Moving on to the record linkage stage, various methods are employed to identify matching records. This stage encompasses deterministic, probabilistic, or

machine learning-based classification strategies, all of which are instrumental in determining the degree of similarity between records. In the final stage, entities that have been successfully resolved as matches in the preceding stage are consolidated to create a singular, representative record. This consolidation step ensures that the merged record accurately represents the linked information, thus concluding the record linkage process (Binette and Steorts, 2022).

Record Linkage tasks encounter a multifaceted trade-off, involving (i) the ability to handle large databases, (ii) ensuring the propagation of uncertainty throughout the entire data cleaning process, and (iii) developing methods that can effectively address the distortions and errors commonly found in databases.

In the context of databases comprising a cumulative total of N records, there exist $N(N - 1)/2$ possible pairs of records that might be correlated, making it infeasible to evaluate each pair as the database size expands. The user should assess the trade-off involving (i), (ii), and (iii) within the context of each specific application to determine the most fitting method (Binette and Steorts, 2022).

1.1.1. Deterministic Record Linkage

Deterministic record linkage is a process that relies on a set of deterministic rules involving the comparison of attributes within records. It encompasses deterministic, rule-based, and similarity-based methods (for references on deterministic algorithm see Adena et al., 2015; Ansolabehere and Hersh, 2017; Berent et al., 2016; Bolsen et al., 2014; Cesarini et al., 2016; Figlio et al., 2014; Giraud-Carrier et al., 2015; Hill, 2017; Meredith and Morse, 2014). For instance, a straightforward example is exact matching, where two record pairs are linked only if they precisely match all common attributes. See Toy Example 1.1 for an illustration of the method.

Toy Example 1.1: Deterministic Record Linkage

Recall the Toy Example 1. We are interested in linking the records of two datasets on energy consumption and sustainability rates. We wonder if “Em Green” (DA.1) and “Emily Green” (DB.3) refer to the same individual; the address is spelled differently although it may appear the same if visually inspected. Similarly for “Sarah Johnson” (DA.3) and “Sarah Johson” (DB.2).

- Common Identifiers: We need to define which are the common identifiers. In this case, all common variables, namely “Name” and “Address” are chosen as matching variables.
- Linkage Rule: Apply a strict rule for exact matches. Spelling errors are not allowed, therefore only records with identical names, ages, and addresses will be linked.
- Outcome: the two pairs of records are not matches.

However, exact matching can be problematic, especially when dealing with data prone to enumeration and transcription errors, as it may exclude a significant number of true matches. While it effectively minimises the occurrence of false positives, it often results in a high rate of false negatives. Additionally, it tends to produce matched samples that are not representative of the overall population. To address these limitations, various strategies have been developed to relax the stringent matching criteria. This can involve allowing a certain number of attribute mismatches,

employing disjunctions of exact matching rules, or utilising similarity functions to gauge the similarity of records. These methods introduce flexibility and accommodate errors in the data, typically implemented through an algorithm that specifies a set of decision rules to determine whether two records are sufficiently similar to be considered a match (see for instance ABE method in Abramitzky et al., 2012, 2014, 2019). However, it's important to note that deterministic approaches lack a built-in mechanism to account for uncertainty in the matching process. They do not employ probability models, nor do they provide a level of confidence in determining the matching status of record pairs. Despite this limitation, deterministic matching approaches can still be valuable, particularly when used as a blocking stage to prepare the data for subsequent probabilistic record linkage methods that incorporate uncertainty considerations. This two-stage approach allows for the scalability of more advanced techniques while benefiting from the efficiency of deterministic rules during the initial stage of record linkage.

1.1.2. Probabilistic Record Linkage

While many social scientists have traditionally relied on deterministic methods for record linkage, probabilistic modelling has emerged as a predominant approach within the statistics literature, especially since the seminal work of Fellegi and Sunter (1969) (see Detail-box 2 for a comparison between deterministic and probabilistic).

Probabilistic record linkage methods fundamentally involve calculating a match score for every possible pairing of records from two different datasets, based on their identifying variables. See Toy Example 1.2 for an illustration of the method. This match score is derived as the sum of the weights assigned to each identifying item used in the matching process. When two records agree for the specific item, a positive weight is assigned; in the case of disagreement of records falling outside a prescribed tolerance, a negative weight is assigned; and if an item is missing in either record, the weight is set to zero. For the treatment of missing variables see Detail-box 1.

Detail-box 1: The issue of Missing Data

The presence of missing data raised issues in record linkage. In the classical literature, often missing data are treated as disagreements (see for instance Goldstein and Harron (2015), Ong et al. (2014) and Sariyar et al. (2012)). This procedure however may end up being problematic because potentially a true match can contain missing values. Some authors tried to develop a framework tackling the problem of missing data in record linkage. For instance, Sadinle (2014), Sadinle (2017) and Enamorado et al. (2019) assume that data are missing at random (MAR) conditional on the match/non-match status, and under this assumption, one can simply ignore the missing data. For a more clear view of the procedure see Enamorado et al. (2019).

The weight allocated to an item is influenced, in part, by how effectively that item distinguishes one entity from another. For instance, when two records share an unusual first name like "Dexter", it suggests a higher likelihood of belonging to the same individual compared to two records with a common first name like "John". Consequently, the item weight for a match involving "Dexter" would be greater than that for a match involving "John". Following the scoring process, each pair of records

can be categorised as a *match*, a *non-match*, or *indeterminate*. Pairs with scores exceeding a predefined cutoff value are identified as matches, indicating substantial agreement on numerous identification variables. Conversely, pairs with scores below a separate cutoff are categorised as non-matches, suggesting disagreements on enough identification variables to indicate distinct entities. If the highest score for a dataset record doesn't reach the non-match cutoff, it's considered to have no corresponding record in the other dataset. Pairs with scores falling between these two cutoff values may necessitate further review before a definitive determination is reached (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2023).

These probabilistic methods are needed in scientific applications where there is a need to account for all sources of uncertainty that might influence the validity of results. The primary challenge in these scenarios lies in accurately quantifying this uncertainty and integrating it into subsequent analyses. These methods are primarily geared towards estimating the probability of a match between pairs of records based on their comparison vectors. This pairwise match score serves as a metric for assessing uncertainty regarding specific links, with false match and false non-match rates (or precision and recall) being metrics for evaluating performance. It is worth noting that, with the exception of Bayesian approaches, most methods treat record pairs as independent entities, often overlooking the implications of transitivity or other constraints within the linkage structure. This limitation can hinder their practicality when linking more than two databases and when dealing with applications featuring duplication across or within databases (Binette and Steorts, 2022).

In a simplified manner, the procedure followed in probabilistic record linkage can be reconstructed in various steps and can be portrayed in the workflow illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: reproduced based on ISTAT (2013)

Toy Example 1.2: Probabilistic Record Linkage

Recall Toy Example 1. We are interested in linking the records of datasets A and B. Probabilistic record linkage allows for a more flexible approach than deterministic approaches, considering the probability that records match based on various factors. It seeks to estimate, for pairs of records, the probability that they are a true match.

- Assumption: We assume conditional independence between the comparison variables given the match status of each pair.
- Common identifiers: As in the previous case, all common variables, namely "Name" and "Address" are chosen as matching variables.
- Linkage rule: A scoring method is used to assess the similarity for each attribute between the two records. For instance, among the many available options, one can choose the Jaro-Winkler distance for string variables, such as "Name" and "Address". Consider the pair DA.1 and DB.3.

Variable	Dataset A	Dataset B	Similarity
Name	Em Green	Emily Green	90%
Address	456 Oak Avenue	456 Oak Ave	95%

Using these similarity scores, a probabilistic record linkage algorithm might calculate the overall probability of a match. One needs to specify a certain threshold above which the records are considered to be a match.

- Outcome: The algorithm determines that there is a high probability of a match based on overall similarity, linking the records and providing a more nuanced understanding of individual sustainability transitions.
- Plus of probabilistic RL: The individuals' matching probability can be incorporated further into the analyses to keep accounting for the matching uncertainty in the inferential procedures.

Detail-box 2: Deterministic vs. probabilistic RL - A comparison

DETERMINISTIC Record Linkage

PROS

- Rules-based approach, simply data join
- Effectively minimizes the occurrence of false positives
- Used as a blocking stage to prepare the data for subsequent probabilistic record linkage methods
- Simplicity, interpretability, and computational scalability

CONS

- These methods are in their basic application not robust to measurement error (e.g., misspelling) and missing data
- Cannot quantify the uncertainty of the merging procedure and instead typically relies on arbitrary thresholds to determine the degree of similarity sufficient for matches
- No probability model is used and no level of confidence is provided for the matching status of record pairs
- High rate of type II errors (false negatives)
- Produces matched samples that are not representative of the overall population

PROBABILISTIC Record Linkage

PROS

- One can estimate the false discovery rate (FDR) and the false negative rate (FNR). Researchers typically select, at their discretion, the value of the threshold such that the FDR is sufficiently small
- Incorporation of auxiliary information in parameter estimation (see Enamorado et al. (2019))
- One can directly incorporate the uncertainty inherent to the merging process in the post-merge analysis
- More matches than exact matching/deterministic matching
- It has the property of requiring no training data for record linkage (it is entirely unsupervised)

CONS

- Not always scalable (especially when entailing high dimensional data and Bayesian approaches)

Classical Approach: The Fellegi-Sunter Model The Fellegi-Sunter framework (Fellegi and Sunter, 1969) formalises the approach of Newcombe et al. (1959) in a decision-theoretic framework. We will review the Fellegi-Sunter probability model, its interpretation, and its underlying assumptions (Binette and Steorts, 2022).

The Fellegi-Sunter framework operates on the principle of making independent decisions for each pair of records. Within this framework, three potential actions are considered for a given record pair: to establish a link, to indicate a possible link, or to abstain from linking altogether. The primary

objective is to strike a delicate balance between minimising the number of potential link assignments and maintaining control over the rates of false matches (Type I error) and false non-matches (Type II error) (see Detail-box 5). The Fellegi-Sunter framework posits that an optimal linkage procedure should achieve the predefined error rates while concurrently minimising the count of potential link assignments. The framework introduces a significant concept known as the “fundamental theorem for record linkage” as established by its authors.

The key idea is that during the linkage process, two specific probabilities must be estimated for each pair of records: $m(\gamma)$, the probability of observing the comparison vector (γ) used to represent the level of agreement/disagreement between two specified records, for two records that are an actual match and $u(\gamma)$, probability of observing the comparison vector for two records that are not a match. It follows that, if γ is an observation generated from the distribution $m(\gamma)$, then the two records are a match.

Instead, if it is generated from $u(\gamma)$, then it can be asserted that the pair is made of two distinct units. This theorem demonstrated by the authors shows that the optimal linkage procedure corresponds to thresholding a likelihood ratio. More details on the model and the decision rule can be found in the Detail-box 3 and 4.

Detail-box 3: Pills of Fellegi and Sunter procedure - Notation (Scanu, 2003)

Let be A and B two partially overlapping files consisting of the same type of unit, for instance, individuals, households, firms, etc. Dataset A has size n_A and dataset B has size n_B .

The set comprising all potential record pairs originating from A and B is denoted as $\Omega = \{(a, b) : a \in A, b \in B\}$. The two files consist of vectors of quantitative and/or qualitative variables (X_A, Y_A) and (X_B, Z_B) . Let us consider X_A and X_B . We are in a setting where these sub-vectors are of k -dimension and thus we have k key variables (common identifiers) such that each unit is uniquely identified by an observation x . Further, let γ_{ab} denote the vector of indicator variables pertaining to the pair of records (a, b) , with $\gamma_{ab} = 1$ in the j -th position if $x_{a,j}^A = x_{b,j}^B$ and 0 otherwise ($j = 1, \dots, k$). These indicators are called *comparison variables*.

We can formally express record linkage as the task of assigning the pair $(a, b \in \Omega)$ to either one of the two subsets, \mathcal{M} or \mathcal{U} . These subsets identify the matched and unmatched sets of pairs, respectively, based on the state of the vector γ_{ab} .

Assuming that the match status is independently and identically distributed, in Fellegi and Sunter (1969) there exists an initial bivariate random variable responsible for allocating each pair of records (a, b) to either the matched records (set \mathcal{M}) or the unmatched ones (set \mathcal{U}). This variable remains latent, or unobserved, serving as the primary objective in the record linkage process. Additionally, the comparison variables follow distinct distributions based on the pair's status.

Let $m(\gamma_{ab})$ represent the distribution of comparison variables when the pair (a, b) is matched (i.e., $(a, b) \in \mathcal{M}$) namely $P(\gamma_{ab} | (a, b) \in \mathcal{M})$, and $u(\gamma_{ab})$ denote the distribution of comparison variables when the pair (a, b) is unmatched (i.e., $(a, b) \in \mathcal{U}$) namely $P(\gamma_{ab} | (a, b) \in \mathcal{U})$. These distributions play a pivotal role in determining the status of record pairs.

Detail-box 4: Pills of Fellegi and Sunter procedure - Model and decision rule (Scanu, 2003)

The primary objective of the entire record linkage process is to ascertain whether a pair of records pertains to the same entity. Consequently, the overall quality of the results obtained through the linkage procedure hinges on the effectiveness of the tool employed to make this assessment, namely, the decision rule. In this procedure, the space of actual outcomes consists of a real match or a real non-match for every pair of records belonging to Ω , and the space \mathcal{D} of all possible decisions consists of assigning or not the pair as a link.

We are then mapping from Ω on Γ , thus mapping from the space of all the potential record pairs to the space of comparison. A function that yields a numerical comparison value for $\gamma_{j,ab}$ multiplied by a weight w_j provides a fundamental score indicating the degree of coincidence for the j -th key variable, determining the contribution of each common identifier. The approach introduced by Fellegi and Sunter (1969) consists of taking into consideration the amount of information provided by each key variable by using a log-likelihood ratio considering the agreement probabilities. Thus a weighted measure of agreement is set and it follows that each pair is then assigned the following weight: $w_{ab} = \log\left(\frac{m(\gamma_{ab})}{u(\gamma_{ab})}\right)$.

The following task is to map from Γ on a space of stated decisions which consists of three possible decisions: A_1 (that is, a link), A_3 (that is, a non-link), and A_2 (that is, a possible link). Each decision has its related probabilities which can be derived from the probability distribution $m(\gamma_{ab})$ and $u(\gamma_{ab})$ and the region of Γ associated to each decision. One can thus view record linkage as a common statistical hypothesis test with a critical and acceptance region. These regions are determined by the varied values of γ in Γ and their corresponding composite weight values, which are then compared against a set of fixed bounds. Additionally, a probability model based on $[m(\gamma_{ab}), u(\gamma_{ab})]$ is required to calibrate error rates, denoted as $\mu = P(A_1|(a, b) \in \mathcal{U})$ and $\lambda = P(A_3|(a, b) \in \mathcal{M})$.

The arrangement of γ_{ab} values should be such that the ratio $R_1(\gamma_{ab}) = m(\gamma_{ab})/u(\gamma_{ab})$ exhibits a monotonically decreasing pattern.

The intuitive meaning of the weight justifies the definition of two thresholds τ_μ and τ_λ , with $\tau_\mu > \tau_\lambda$, dependent on fixed values μ and λ , where $0 < \lambda < 1$ and $0 < \mu < 1$.

- $(a, b) \in A_1$ (link), when the ratio is bigger than or equal to τ_μ
- $(a, b) \in A_2$ (possible link) when the ratio is comprised in the region between τ_μ and τ_λ
- $(a, b) \in A_3$ (non-link) when the ratio is lower than or equal to with τ_λ

The thresholds are assigned solving equations that minimise both the size of the set of possible links and the false match rate and false non-match rate.

Figure 4 describes how the optimal rule works in a Fellegi-Sunter framework. Vertical lines in the diagram depict the thresholds. The left line denotes the lower threshold, while the right line denotes the upper threshold. The regions labelled FU and FM indicate the probabilities of false non-matches (FU) and false matches (FM). These regions correspond to the associated error rates for false nonmatches and false matches, respectively.

Figure 4: F-S optimal rule

The probabilistic record linkage framework operates based on two critical independence assumptions:

1. The latent (unobserved) variable that describes the match status is assumed to be independently and identically distributed.
2. The independence of comparison vectors among record pairs; this is the Conditional Independence Assumption (CIA) i.e., the assumption of independence between the comparison variables given the match status of each pair.

However, these assumptions often face challenges in practical applications. They often require transitivity closure within linkages, meaning that if a record links to another (a links to b) and that a second record links to a third (b links to c), it should imply that the first record links to the third (a links to c). Achieving transitivity closure can be complex and is not commonly realised in practice. Moreover, concerning the feasibility of estimating m and u distributions, the presence of latent

variable risks makes the model parameter unidentified, and often methods rely on simplifying assumptions that may not be valid. Since these assumptions frequently do not align with the complexities encountered in real-world scenarios, numerous extensions and variations have been developed in the literature to address these limitations. We provide an overview of these extensions in the “Modern probabilistic record linkage” section, highlighting how researchers have expanded upon the Fellegi-Sunter framework to accommodate more nuanced and practical situations.

The other key aspect is related to the definition of the above-mentioned thresholds. It is important to note that the Fellegi-Sunter theory does not offer specific guidelines for establishing the thresholds to determine matches or non-matches. Instead, it operates on the principle that one can minimize Type I error (false positives) at the expense of Type II error (false negatives) or vice versa by setting these thresholds. Fellegi-Sunter proposes that a manual review of record pairs across a range of assigned weights can be conducted. This manual review aids in the identification of thresholds above which pairs are highly likely to be matches and below which pairs are highly likely to be non-matches. This empirical approach enables the fine-tuning of the thresholds based on the specific needs and characteristics of the dataset, ensuring that the linkage process aligns with the desired balance between minimising false positives and false negatives (Asher et al., 2020).

Detail-box 5: False matches and false non-matches

Let's consider:

- true positives: n_m
- false positives: n_{fp}
- true negatives: n_u
- false negatives: n_{fn}
- the total number of true matches: N_m
- the total number of true non-matches: N_u

We can then define the **false match rate** as the number of incorrectly linked record pairs divided by the total number of linked record pairs:

$$FMR = \frac{n_{fp}}{(n_m + n_{fp})}$$

It can be seen as the probability of the Type I error and thus corresponds to the significance α in a one-tail hypothesis test.

Analogously we can define the **false non-match rate** as the number of incorrectly unlinked record pairs divided by the total number of true match record pairs:

$$FNMR = \frac{n_{fn}}{N_m}$$

It corresponds to the probability of the Type II error, thus the probability β in a one-tail hypothesis test.

Modern Approaches to Record Linkage As mentioned in the previous sections, a crucial element in the application of probabilistic rules for record linkage revolves around the distributions of comparison variables corresponding to matches and non-matches, respectively. However, these distributions are typically unknown and necessitate estimation. Thus, the focus of the advancement in methods following the approaches by Fellegi and Sunter (1969) went in the direction of strategies for the estimation of these distributions. As described above, at the core of this framework is the idea that all pairs of records are assumed to be independently generated by a mixture of two distributions—one for matched pairs and another for unmatched ones. The assignment of matched and unmatched status to pairs is determined randomly by a latent (i.e., unobserved) dichotomous variable. In this section, we review modern probabilistic record linkage methods and their different approaches in estimation, which include extensions to the Fellegi-Sunter framework, Bayesian variants of Fellegi-Sunter, as well as machine learning semi-supervised and fully supervised classification approaches (Binette and Steorts, 2022)

1) Extensions to F-S The model described above facilitates the computation of a likelihood function to be maximised for estimating the unknown distributions of the comparison variables for matched and non-matched pairs. Since we are in the presence of a latent (unobserved) variable, the maximisation of the likelihood function typically involves iterative methods for handling it, commonly the EM algorithm or some of its generalisations

One of the primary directions for extending record linkage methods has focused on refining the criteria for setting thresholds (see Belin and Rubin, 1995). Part of the reason is that the error rates fixed in the Fellegi-Sunter framework, as well as the estimated false match rates, are not attained in practice. This discrepancy arises from several factors, including the simplifying assumptions and estimation errors inherent in the application of such probabilistic models. Moreover Winkler et al. (2000); Winkler (2002), and Larsen and Rubin (2001) instead considered fitting more complex models, allowing dependencies between field comparisons. Larsen and Rubin (2001) developed an iterative approach to lower as much as possible the number of records whose status was uncertain. Important to mention is the recent computational and methodological work of Enamorado et al. (2019) who scaled the F-S model to large databases, where they incorporated auxiliary information in the merge to inform parameter estimation and post-merge analyses which accounts for the uncertainty about the merge process.

2) Bayesian F-S Bayesian techniques rely on probabilities of a match or non-match for specific agreement patterns that are either based on expert opinion or previous projects. For example, one may be interested in linking two datasets containing the English equivalents of Arabic names, such as for the Syrian data in Tancredi et al. (2020). Assume to have information on how the transliteration was obtained; such information may be formally included in the probabilities of match and non-match via appropriate prior elicitation. As is typical in a Bayesian approach, the prior information is then combined with the data, in with a new record linkage process involving new lists. At the end of the process, a posterior probability of match or non-match is determined for the record pairs, which allows the determination of links and non-links (Asher et al., 2020). Bayesian methods provide a way to quantify and propagate uncertainty for the joint linkage structure of a set of records (see for more detail Section 1.1.3 and Detail-box 6).

In the basic Bayesian Fellegi-Sunter framework the m and u probabilities were assumed to follow a probability distribution of some type; for example, a uniform distribution with all possible probability values being equally likely, or a Beta distribution, with the parameters of the distribution set based on expert knowledge. The optimal (mean) values from the posterior distributions of the m and u probabilities were then used to create the match weights and complete the linkage process.

For a simple example of a Bayesian model, have a look at Detail-box 6.

Several Bayesian extensions have been proposed in the literature and can be found in Fortini et al. (2001), Sadinle (2014), Sadinle (2017), Marchant et al. (2021), Tancredi and Liseo (2011), Ventura and Nugent (2014), McVeigh et al. (2019). In particular, McVeigh et al. (2019) addresses one of the main issues of the Bayesian approaches, which is their computational burden, which makes them difficult to implement with large datasets. They propose a blocking approach based on simpler probabilistic record linkage techniques. That is, the output of a simpler non-Bayesian probabilistic record linkage is used to perform “post hoc blocking”, after which a Bayesian Fellegi-Sunter method is used for coherent modelling and uncertainty quantification. This allows the authors to scale their proposed method to voter registration and census datasets with millions of entries.

3) Machine Learning Approaches Computer science researchers have approached data linkage from a traditional binary supervised classification perspective (with the two classes being “matches” and “non-matches”, but with no “potential matches”), or from a clustering perspective (where the aim is to group all records that refer to the same entity into one cluster) (Christen, 2019).

In machine learning, probabilistic record linkage can be replaced by one of several classification algorithms, whose goal is the creation of 3 clusters (links, non-links, possible links) which are formed to match the three regions of match weights in the Fellegi-Sunter algorithm (Asher et al., 2020). The ML approaches can be divided into:

- **SUPERVISED:** a training set of data is used to “teach” a classification algorithm, such as decision trees, support vector machines, ensemble methods (i.e., random forests), or conditional random fields.
- **UNSUPERVISED:** a method that does not rely on training data. An example is k-means clustering. In k-means clustering, for each pair, a measure of similarity for each field is calculated. Multiple similarity measures have been used within unsupervised record linkage Asher et al. (2020).

Once each of the pairs of records has an associated similarity measure vector, the distance between different pairs of records is measured. Different distance measures can be used, a common one is the Euclidean distance (i.e., summing the squared distance across all the fields being compared). Record pairs that are “close” to each other according to the distance measure are formed into clusters.

Fully supervised methods do not exploit the information provided by unlabelled examples; instead, they rely on larger numbers of labelled pairs. Given the significant class imbalance when considering record pairs (very few pairs match), vast amounts of reliable training data or carefully selected training data are required for the use of these methods. These training data may come from crowdsourcing or extensive manual record linkage efforts or they may be automatically generated

using unsupervised methods to obtain an approximate training set. However, in practice, the amount of reliable training data necessary to train sophisticated learning algorithms such as deep neural networks are not always available for record linkage tasks. Some examples can be found in Kooli et al. (2018) and Kasai et al. (2019). Moreover, the use of deep learning techniques in entity resolution is especially promising in application to unstructured or textual problems, where, for instance, pre-trained language models can be used. For structured record linkage, simple classifiers (such as logistic regression, decision trees, random forests, Bayesian additive regression trees, and others) are often preferred.

Clustering-based approaches to record linkage can integrate multiple databases (Sadinle (2014), Sadinle (2017), Marchant et al. (2021), Tancredi and Liseo (2011), Ventura and Nugent (2014) etc.). Many clustering approaches to entity resolution are based on pairwise similarities, pairwise match probabilities, or determined links and non-links. Therefore, they can be seen as post-processing the result of other pairwise record linkage procedures. Clustering can be for instance used as a postprocessing step, namely as a second step to probabilistic record linkage to enforce transitivity of the output (for a review and concrete examples see Christophides et al., 2020; Monge, 1997; Ventura and Nugent, 2014).

1.1.3. The problem of assessing uncertainty

As emphasised multiple times throughout this discussion, an essential concern in the realm of record linkage and the creation of a synthetic dataset, particularly in the context of post-merge analysis, revolves around the evaluation of the uncertainty inherent in the linkage process. It is crucial to acknowledge that the linkage process is inherently imperfect, introducing a layer of error that further compounds the uncertainties present in statistical analyses. Remarkably, linkage errors are seldom, if at all, considered in the realms of inference or data dissemination. This absence of attention to linkage error means that its potential impact on the accuracy and reliability of data-driven conclusions remains largely unaddressed, highlighting the need for more comprehensive strategies to quantify and manage such uncertainties (for more detail see among other Reiter, 2021).

The general sources of uncertainty in Record Linkage are:

- 1. Imperfect Matching:** Numerous record linkage methods result in a consolidated dataset containing a collection of record pairs that are considered the best matches based on specific criteria. In situations where perfect and unique identifiers are not available, this set may inadvertently include false matches. Furthermore, measurement errors can extend to the blocking variables used in the linkage process, further complicating the determination of true matches. The presence of these false matches can present challenges when drawing inferences from the linked data. When aggregated across many individuals, these errors can significantly distort estimates of the variables of interest, as well as their associated standard errors.
- 2. Incomplete Matching:** Incomplete matching in the context of record linkage signifies that not all individuals from the primary dataset find corresponding counterparts in the secondary dataset. Incomplete matching can introduce a subtle yet impactful “selection mechanism” that has the potential to skew the outcomes of statistical inferences. Even in cases where no overt

selection mechanisms are at play, and the linkage process can be considered “ignorable” for the analysis (as defined by Rubin, 1976), it is important to recognise that solely utilising linked cases results in the partial utilisation of available information. This selective approach can lead to inflated variances in the inferences drawn.

Researchers have developed a variety of approaches to account for uncertainties in record linkage. The most common are: (i) modelling the matching matrix that indicates who matches whom as a parameter, (ii) embedding the linkage in a particular modelling task, and (iii) the imputation of incomplete links to address biases from incomplete matching.

Concerning the former, one effective approach is to leverage Bayesian methodologies, as exemplified in works like those by Fortini et al. (2001), Tancredi and Liseo (2011), Sadinle (2017). For more details on the Bayesian approach to account for uncertainty see Detail-box 6.

To account for the uncertainty in the linkage process, one can also embed the record linkage process directly in an analysis model, usually some regression involving (potentially multivariate) X and Y, to incorporate uncertainty in the inferences. Methods for doing so take two main forms: the adjustment approach (see Detail-box 7) and the use of hierarchical models. For the latter approach, the method implies the use of multiple imputations to fill in missing items for non-matched cases (for more details see Gutman et al., 2013).

Detail-box 6: Bayesian Example

Suppose every record k in File A or File B has L linking variables, (d_{k1}, \dots, d_{kL}) for $l = 1, \dots, L$ and all pairs of records (i, j) where i comes from File A and j from File B. Define the binary comparison variable e_{ijl} such that $e_{ijl} = 1$ when $d_{i1} = d_{j1}$ and $e_{ijl} = 0$ otherwise. Here, the analyst can compute $e_{ij} = e_{ij1}, \dots, e_{ijL}$ for all (i, j) pairs. The Bayesian modelling approach specifies a data model for the (vector-valued) random variables E_{ij} for all (i, j) given the unknown C , coupled with a prior distribution on C . In general, this model allows for the possibility that one or more $e_{ijl} = 0$ when $c_{ij} = 1$, for example, due to recording or measurement errors in the different files, and the possibility that $e_{ijl} = 1$ for many or even all l when $c_{ij} = 0$. Thus, the usual approach in Bayesian record linkage is to specify (at least) one model for cases where $c_{ij} = 1$, i.e. the matches, and another model for cases where $c_{ij} = 0$, i.e. the non-matches. Mathematically, we can write this as

$$E_{ij}|c_{ij} = 1 \sim f(\theta_m)$$

$$E_{ij}|c_{ij} = 0 \sim f(\theta_u)$$

where θ_m are parameters for the model corresponding to matches and θ_u are parameters for the model corresponding to non-matches. Assume independent Bernoulli distributions; for $l = 1, \dots, L$, assume $Pr(E_{ijl} = 1|c_{ij} = 1) = \theta_{ml}$ and $Pr(E_{ijl} = 1|c_{ij} = 0) = \theta_{ul}$.

The second step is to specify a prior distribution on C , which can be done in many ways. First, we specify a model for the number of matches, i.e. for $n_m = \sum_{ij} c_{ij}$; this can be expressed through prior beliefs on the proportion of matches, which can be modelled using a simple Beta distribution with parameters tuned to reflect prior expectations. Second, conditional on knowing n_m records match, we assume all possible bipartite matching are equally likely. A key advantage of using such prior distributions is that they can easily enforce one-to-one matching. The resulting model can be estimated using relatively straightforward Gibbs sampling techniques. The result is a posterior distribution on C that summarises the uncertainty in the linkage (under the posited model).

For example, with enough posterior draws, for any record i in File A, one can estimate the posterior probabilities that any record j in File B is its match; simply, one computes the percentage of times record j is matched to record i across the runs. We note that the Bayesian approach extends beyond binary comparison vectors. It can be used to handle levels of agreement, as well as missing values in the linking variables (Sadinle, 2017).

Detail-box 7: Simple Model for Adjustment Approach

The general idea of this approach is to use estimates of the matching probabilities of the linkage process to adjust point estimates of regression coefficients (see, Scheuren and Winkler (1993) Scheuren and Winkler (1997); Lahiri and Larsen (2005), Enamorado et al. (2019)). Suppose we are interested in estimating the regression

$$y_i = \mathbf{x}'_i \beta + \epsilon_i$$

where $\epsilon_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$ for all i .

In this case, the regression with incorrectly linked data is actually based on the outcome z_i rather than y_i where

$$Pr(z_i = y_i) = q_{ii} \quad ; \quad Pr(z_i = y_j) = q_{ij} \quad \text{for } i \neq j$$

q_{ij} is the probability that record j is the correct link for record i , where j ranges over all records in File B that could be matched to record i in File A. Using OLS to regress Z on X results in a biased estimate of β , since $E(z_i) = \mathbf{w}'_i \beta$, where $\mathbf{w}_i = \sum_j q_{ij} \mathbf{x}'_j$. Scheuren and Winkler (1993) suggest an approach to approximate the bias in a naive estimate of β , based on estimating various q_{ij} from the outputs of the linkage procedure. Moreover Lahiri and Larsen (2005), extended the approach to derive an unbiased estimator of β .

$$\hat{\beta}_{LL} = (\mathbf{W}'\mathbf{W})^{-1} \mathbf{W}'\mathbf{Z}$$

where \mathbf{Z} is the vector of outcomes in the linked file and \mathbf{W} is a the matrix $(\mathbf{w}'_1, \dots, \mathbf{w}'_n)$ of the linear transformation of \mathbf{X} ; $\mathbf{w}_i = \mathbf{q}'_i \mathbf{X} = \sum_j q_{ij} \mathbf{x}'_j$
For more detail on possible adjustment approaches also in the case of a merged variable as an outcome variable or as an explanatory variable see Enamorado et al. (2019).

1.2. Statistical Matching

Statistical matching refers to a family of methods aiming at the integration of two or more datasets drawn from the same target population, that contain information on a set of common variables, X , and some not jointly observed variables, (Y, Z) . Different from record linkage, statistical matching deals with data sources whose units are not necessarily overlapping.

There are two main approaches to statistical matching: a *macro approach* and a *micro approach*. On the one hand, the macro approach to statistical matching aims at directly estimating the joint model of the variables of interest that are not jointly observed. On the other hand, the micro approach is devoted to the generation of a synthetic dataset with complete information on the variables observed only in one data source and those observed in two data sources. The dataset produced as an output of the procedure is said to be *complete* because all the variables of interest are contained in it; it is said to be *synthetic* because it is not a product of direct observation of a set of units in the population of interest, but it is obtained by exploiting information in the source files in some appropriate ways. The boundary between the two approaches is not clearly defined. Although the main objective of the macro approach is not the creation of a complete dataset, a synthetic dataset may be obtained as a by-product of the estimation procedure; We will briefly discuss this approach in Section 1.2.3.

In practice, matching procedures devoted to the creation of a complete dataset can be regarded as an imputation problem of the target variables from a donor to a recipient survey (D'Orazio et al., 2006). The relation between the common variables with the target variables observed only in one of the datasets -the donor dataset- is explored and used to impute to the units of the other dataset -the

recipient dataset- the variables that are not directly observed (see Detail-box 8) Thus, a synthetic dataset is generated with complete information on the target variables and the common ones.

Toy Example 2: Creation of of a synthetic dataset via statistical matching

Here is another example of a complication one can encounter in dealing with data integration when the aim is to create a synthetic dataset. As in the first toy example, let us suppose we have two distinct datasets that are collecting information on sustainability practices and energy consumption of individuals in Ireland. Specifically, dataset A collects information on energy consumption, whereas dataset B includes data on recycling rates. In this application, we do not care about the design behind the datasets. The two datasets collect information on the same target population of individuals, but, in this case, we do not have quasi-identifier variables (i.e., name and address). The only common information we have are four common variables that describe the individuals and their households.

DATASET A: CITIZEN						DATASET B: CITIZEN					
ID	Gender	Age	Annual utility expense (in euro)	# household members	Monthly Energy Consumption:	ID	Gender	Age	Annual utility expense (in euro)	# household members	Recycling Rate:
DA.1	F	36	4,250	6	500 kWh	DB.1	F	28	1,300	1	95%
DA.2	M	42	2,000	2	300 kWh	DB.2	F	28	3,700	3	75%
DA.3	F	28	3,300	4	400 kWh	DB.3	M	37	4,750	6	80%
DA.4	M	39	1,150	1	250 kWh	DB.4	M	40	1,800	2	40%

The aim is to integrate the two data sources leveraging the common variables to study the relationship between the two sets of variables not jointly observed, in this case "monthly energy consumption" and "recycling rate". Thus, the objective is to create a complete "synthetic" dataset, where for each row (a record) none of the variables is missing. Since we do not observe all the variables jointly, we need to leverage statistical methods to exploit the information contained in the distinct files.

Differently from record linkage, when setting a statistical matching procedure it is essential to explicit our assumptions. The most common situation is when the variables that are never jointly observed are assumed to be independent conditionally on the available covariates; this is the *Conditional Independence Assumption* (CIA; see Detail-box 8).

Detail-box 8: Conditional Independence Assumption

Consider two datasets A and B ; we observe (Y, X) in A and (Z, X) in B . Denote with $f(Y, Z, X)$ the joint distribution of Y, Z, X . For the rules of probability, we can write

$$f(Y, Z, X) = f(Y | Z, X)f(Z | X)f(X) ,$$

where $f(Y | Z, X)$ is unknown because we never observe Y and Z jointly. We say that Y and Z are conditionally independent given X , i.e., $Y \perp\!\!\!\perp Z | X$, if we can write

$$f(Y, Z, X) = f(Y | X)f(Z | X)f(X) .$$

Now, the elements on the right-hand side of the equation above are all known.

Under the CIA, statistical matching procedures ensure that the marginal and joint distribution of the variables in the source files is reflected in the statistically matched file (Rässler, 2012). Any discrepancy between the real data generation model and the underlying model of the synthetic complete dataset is called “matching noise”.

Statistical matching can be performed in a parametric and a nonparametric framework.

1.2.1 Parametric micro approach

Consider two data sources A and B ; we observe (Y, X) in A and (Z, X) in B . We are interested in learning something about the joint distribution of Y and Z (or Y, Z, X). Under the CIA, the joint relation between the common variables and the variables not jointly observed can be modelled (see Detail-box 8). In other words, we assume a parametric model for the joint distributions of (Y, X) and (Z, X) . Once the parametric model is estimated, Z is imputed for each unit in A and Y is imputed for each unit in B . For the imputation, different techniques, such as conditional mean imputation and imputation from a distribution, can be implemented. See Toy Example 2.1 for an illustration of the method.

Toy Example 2.1: Parametric micro approach to statistical matching

Recall the Toy Example 2.

- Assumption: We assume conditional independence between the monthly energy consumption (Y) and the recycling rate (Z) given the other variables.
- Common variables: For the sake of simplicity, in this toy example, one could consider just one common variable, e.g., annual utility expense (X). More expert readers may be familiar with the matrix notation $\mathbf{X} = (X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4)$, where the variable X is now a vector of variables; in other words, the set of common variables include gender (X_1), age (X_2), annual utility expense (X_3) and no. of household members (X_4).
- Approach: Parametric.

1. We assume a parametric model on the relation between the monthly energy consumption and the annual utility expense, e.g.,

$$\log Y_i = \alpha + \beta X_i + \varepsilon_i$$

for all units i in dataset A. We estimate the model via OLS or maximum likelihood and obtain $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$. Using the estimates and the annual utility expense of all units j in dataset B, we can impute the monthly energy consumption \hat{Y}_j , e.g., drawing values from the estimated model.

2. We assume a parametric model on the relation between the recycling rate and the annual utility expense, e.g.,

$$\log Z_j = \gamma + \delta X_j + \eta_j$$

for all units j in dataset B. We estimate the model via OLS or maximum likelihood and obtain $\hat{\gamma}$ and $\hat{\delta}$. Using the estimates and the annual utility expense of all units i in dataset A, we can impute the recycling rate \hat{Z}_i , e.g., drawing values from the estimated model.

- Outcome: A complete synthetic dataset as follows, where the bold entries are estimates from the models described above:

ID	Gender	Age	Annual utility expense (in euro)	# of household members	Monthly energy consumption	Recycling rate
DA.1	F	36	4,250	6	500 kWh	73%
DA.2	M	42	2,000	2	300 kWh	67%
DA.3	F	28	3,300	4	400 kWh	65%
DA.4	M	39	1,150	1	250 kWh	72%
DB.1	F	28	1,300	1	489 kWh	95%
DB.2	F	28	3,700	3	308 kWh	75%
DB.3	M	37	4,750	6	413 kWh	80%
DB.4	M	40	1,800	2	240 kWh	40%

1.2.2. Nonparametric micro approach

When we do not want to consider the possibility of assuming a distribution in advance, nonparametric frameworks are favored. One possibility is to use nonparametric estimation techniques to infer the relations between X and Y , and X and Z and then proceed as under the parametric framework just described. Another possibility is to avoid the estimation step and fill the missing values with existing ones; these kinds of procedures belong to the *hot deck* imputation family.

Especially when the matching variables are categorical, a popular technique is the “random hot deck”. It consists of randomly choosing a record in the donor file for each record in the recipient file. The pairing is often done within strata or donation classes; their function is similar to the “blocking variables” of record linkage procedures. Whereas in the case of quantitative variables, the most popular nonparametric techniques are the “Distance Hot Deck” ones (Okner, 1972; Rodgers, 1984; Ruggles and Ruggles, 1974); each record in the recipient file is matched with the closest record in the donor file, according to a distance measure computed using the matching variables. When two or more donor records are equally distant from the recipient record, one of them is chosen at random.

When each record in the donor file can be used as a donor only once, the distance hot deck procedure is said to be “constrained”. The main advantage of a constrained hot deck approach is that the marginal distribution of the imputed variable is maintained in the final synthetic file. On the other hand, the average distance of the donor and recipient values of the matching variables X is expected to be greater than that in an unconstrained case. D’Orazio et al. (2006) underlines the importance of the choice of the recipient file, which is usually the one to be used as the basis for further statistical analyses. For the sake of accuracy, as a rule of thumb, when the sizes of the two data sources are very different it is better to choose the smallest to be the recipient. In this way, the risk that the distribution of the imputed variable does not reflect the original one (estimated from the donor dataset) is low.

The R package StatMatch (D’Orazio, 2022) refers to the distance hot deck method as “nearest neighbor distance hot deck”, and implements it in the function `NND.hotdeck` (see Section 3 for references on the R packages to implement statistical matching). The function searches in the donor file the nearest neighbor of each unit in the recipient file according to a distance function computed on the matching variables. To reduce the effort in computing distances, D’Orazio (2011) suggests defining some donation classes, usually defined according to one or more categorical common variables.

For a simple example, see Toy Example 2.2.

Toy Example 2.2: Nonparametric micro approach to statistical matching

Recall the Toy Example 2.

- Assumption: We assume conditional independence between the monthly energy consumption (Y) and the recycling rate (Z) given the other variables.
- Common variables: For the sake of simplicity, in this toy example, one could consider just one common variable, e.g., annual utility expense (X). See the previous Detail-box for the generalisation to the multivariate case.
- Approach: Nonparametric - distance hot deck. It consists of two steps:
 1. Assign to either dataset A or B the role of the recipient: Let us give dataset A the role of the recipient.
 2. For each record in dataset A, measure the distance between its value of the matching variable X , namely the annual income, and the value of X of each record in B.

ID	DB.1 DB.2 DB.3 DB.4				
	X	1.3	3.7	4.75	1.8
DA.1	4.25	4.25-1.3 =2.95	4.25-3.7 =0.55	 4.25-4.75 =0.5	4.25-1.8 =2.45
DA.2	2	2-1.3 =0.7	2-3.7 =1.7	2-4.75 =2.75	 2-1.8 =0.2
DA.3	3.3	3.3-1.3 =2	 3.3-0.37 =0.4	3.3-4.75 =1.45	3.3-1.8 =0.15
DA.4	1.15	 1.15-1.3 =0.15	0.115-3.7 =2.55	1.15-4.75 =3.6	1.15-1.8 =0.65

- Outcome: The pairs of records with the minimum distance (above in bold) become matches.

ID	Gender	Age	Annual utility expense	# of Household	Monthly energy consumption	Matched ID	Recycling rate
DA.1	F	36	4.25	3	300 kWh	DB.3	75%
DA.2	M	42	2	1	250 kWh	DB.1	40%
DA.3	F	28	3.3	2	400 kWh	DB.2	80%
DA.4	M	39	1.15	0	350 kWh	DB.4	95%

1.2.3. Macro approach

Beyond the micro approach described in the previous sections, statistical matching provides another apparently different way to pursue data integration: the so-called *macro* approach (D'Orazio et al., 2006).

The macro approach uses the source files in order to have a direct estimation of the joint distribution function (or of some of its key characteristics, such as the correlation) of the variables of interest that have not been observed in common.

Most of the statistical matching methods are built on the aforementioned CIA. If the CIA holds, the joint density of the variables of interest in the two data sources and the matching variables can be

factorised into the product of conditional densities (the pairwise relationship between the target variables and the matching ones) times the marginal density of the matching variables; this way, the model is identifiable and the macro approach consists of directly estimating it.

It is important to underline that the CIA cannot be tested; it could be a wrong and misleading assumption if it is introduced when it does not hold.

1.2.4 Assessing uncertainty

As mentioned before, the CIA cannot be tested since the variables of interest y and z are never jointly observed; when it is likely to be a misspecified assumption, more *uncertainty* must be yielded in the model.

In particular, as firstly suggested by Rubin (1986), one should consider a set of plausible parameters rather than a point estimate and generate a collection of synthetic datasets, rather than a single one. In the context of *multiple imputation*, fully Bayesian techniques are well-suited.

Detail-box 9: Statistical matching uncertainty

D'Orazio et al. (2006) formally define the statistical matching uncertainty. Assume to know exactly the partial joint distributions of (Y, X) and (Z, X) , and denote with θ_{YX} and θ_{ZX} the parameters of such distributions. Denote with $\theta \in \Theta$ the unknown parameter, defined in the parameter space Θ , defining the full joint distribution of (Y, X, Z) . If the CIA does not hold, we still can say that the plausible values of θ are those belonging to a subset of Θ , Θ^{SM} that satisfies the constraints given by the values of θ_{YX} and θ_{ZX} .

2. Combining probability and nonprobability samples

Probability sampling continues to be the gold standard for acquiring a representative sample: in probability samples, the selection probability is known and therefore the estimations from a probability sample can rely on well-known statistical inference methods, often design-based. Nonetheless, the measurement of the study variable can also be derived from a non-probability sample or from *big data* sources.

The increasingly high costs for probability surveys, coupled with high non-response rates and the need to provide information at more granular levels have led to the necessity over time to integrate information from multiple sources.

Initially, methods were suggested for integrating multiple probability samples. Recently, in survey statistics, there has been a surge in the availability of nonprobability data for research purposes, offering unprecedented opportunities for new scientific discoveries.

However, they also pose additional challenges, including issues such as heterogeneity, selection bias, high dimensionality, and more. Specifically, this has emphasized the necessity to propose new suitable methods for combining probability and emerging nonprobability samples, as well as for merging probability samples with big nonprobability datasets as outlined in the review given by Yang and Kim (2020). Before describing these methods, let's briefly review the techniques for integrating probability samples.

Existing methods for probability data integration can be classified into two types, depending on the level of information to be combined: a macro approach combining the summary statistics from multiple surveys, and a micro approach creating synthetic imputations.

The macro approach was employed to combine data from two independent probability samples for estimating totals at the population and domain levels by Renssen and Nieuwenbroek (1997), Hidiroglou (2001), Merkouris (2004), Wu (2004), Ybarra and Lohr (2008), and (Merkouris, 2010). (Merkouris, 2004) and Merkouris (2010) provided a rigorous treatment of the survey integration through the generalized method of moments. Fuller and J. (1999) describe an application in the National Resource Inventory.

Very briefly, the proposals in this approach seek to devise a composite estimation method for aligning estimators of common characteristics in scenarios involving multiple surveys on the same population or multiple samples within the same survey. In addition, they allow to generate more efficient estimators for non-common variables, exploiting the strength of their correlation with the common ones.

In the micro approach, mass imputation (also called synthetic data imputation) is the commonly used technique for creating imputed values for items not observed in the current survey by incorporating information from other surveys. For simplicity, let's consider the case of two probability samples, a small sample A and a large sample B. In sample A, observe auxiliary

information X and outcome Y , whereas in sample B , observe common auxiliary information X . The primary goal is to create proxy values of Y for the units in B , and then to use these values together with the associated sample weights in B to produce projection estimators. The proxy values are generated by first fitting a working model relating Y to X , based on the data from sample A used as a sort of training sample.

When we have more datasets and the missingness structure is not monotone, the mass imputation is still used but it becomes more complicated. A sample with partial information may contain additional information for parameter estimation. In such a situation a joint model of all variables needs to be considered, and the EM algorithm can be used to estimate the model parameters. Kim et al. (2016) used an instrumental variable assumption for model identification and developed fractional imputation methods for statistical matching. Park and Kim (2016) presented an application of the statistical matching technique using fractional imputation in the context of handling mixed-mode surveys. Park et al. (2017) applied the method to combine two surveys with measurement errors.

Toy Example 3: Combining probability and nonprobability samples

Suppose we are interested in estimating the average household's monthly energy consumption of our target population, but the only available information comes from energy suppliers; thus, in statistical terms, it is a nonprobability sample. This dataset is the synthetic dataset that was created by integrating Dataset A and Dataset B with one of the data integration techniques explained in Toy Example 1 or Toy Example 2. Let us suppose the dataset supplied by the energy suppliers (Dataset AB) was created by us using Record Linkage techniques.

If we simply use this data source to make inferences, for instance, to investigate the relationship between "recycling rate" and "monthly energy consumption" or to compute the average of "monthly energy consumption" in the target population, our estimate will be biased. The bias arises from the nonprobability nature of Dataset AB. Indeed, we do not know if Dataset AB represents the target population since it is a nonprobability sample and we do not know the selection mechanism governing the selection of individuals into the sample.

However, luckily we know that the National Institute of Ireland annually surveys Irish households and their consumption behaviours (probability sample) therefore we know we have access to auxiliary variable information (i.e., a set of common covariates) from this probability survey sample (Dataset P). Multiple methods can be used to leverage this information coming from different data sources to make a reliable and representative inference and estimate the average household's monthly energy consumption.

- **Dataset AB (Nonprobability Sample):**

Y = monthly energy consumption

Z = recycling rate

X = gender, age, annual utility expense, no. of household members, urban/rural, type of dwelling

- **Dataset P (Probability Survey Sample):**

X = gender, age, annual utility expense, no. of household members, urban/rural, type of dwelling

The aim is to estimate the average household's monthly energy consumption μ_y . As mentioned above, because the sampling mechanism of a nonprobability sample is unknown, the target population quantity is not identifiable in general. Indeed, the sampling mechanism of dataset AB is unknown and, therefore, μ_y is not identifiable in general.

Toy Example 3: Visualization of Nonprobability Synthetic Dataset & Probability Dataset

DATASET AB: CITIZEN & HOUSEHOLDS

ID	Name	Address	Gender	Age	Annual utility expense (in euro)	# household members	Urban/rural	Type of dwelling	Monthly Energy Consumption	Recycling Rate
DAB. 1	Emma Murphy	42 Oak Street	F	35	2,630.00	3	Urban	Apartment	300 kWh	95%
DAB. 2	Sarah Johson	102 Maple Driv	F	28	3,300.00	4	Rural	Detached House	400 kWh	75%
DAB. 3	Emily Green	456 Oak Ave	F	36	4,250.00	6	Urban	Apartment	500 kWh	80%
DAB. 4	Liam O'Sullivan	15 Birch Avenue	M	40	1,370.00	1	Urban	Loft	200 kWh	70%

DATASET P: HOUSEHOLD NATIONAL SURVEY ON CONSUMPTION

ID	Gender	Age	Annual utility expense (in euro)	# household members	Urban/rural	Type of dwelling
DP.1	F	28	3,200.00	3	Urban	Apartment
DP.2	M	35	4,500.00	5	Rural	Apartment
DP.3	F	45	2,800.00	2	Urban	Apartment
DP.4	M	30	3,800.00	4	Rural	Detached House

2.1. Dealing with the biased nonprobability samples

As outlined in the "Summary Report of the AAPOR Task Force on Nonprobability Sampling" by Baker et al. (2013), unlike probability sampling, there is no single framework that comprehensively encompasses all nonprobability sampling. However, all nonprobability samples share some common traits. First, they operate with unknown selection or inclusion mechanisms; second, they tend to be biased; third, they may not faithfully represent the target population. Nevertheless, nonprobability samples are readily available data sources that are more cost-effective and quicker to obtain. Consequently, a central focus for many survey sampling researchers in recent years has been addressing the challenge of developing methods to derive valid statistical inferences from these samples. A review is given in Wu (2022).

All these methods stem from the recognition that generating valid inferences from nonprobability samples requires additional information from the target population. The likelihood of having access to complete auxiliary information is typically implausible in most scenarios. A popular framework is to assume that auxiliary variable information on the same population is available from an existing probability survey sample called reference probability sample. This framework was first used by Rivers (2007) and followed by several other authors including Vavreck and Rivers (2008), Lee and

Valliant (2009), Valliant and Dever (2011), Elliott (2017), and Chen et al. (2020), among others. Existing methods for integrating data from a probability sample and a nonprobability sample can be classified into the four types described in the following subsections respectively. However, one needs first to outline which are the assumptions needed to pursue the following data integrating techniques (see Detailbox 10). The main assumptions are three:

A1 The auxiliary variables included in the nonprobability sample fully characterise the participation behaviour or the sample inclusion mechanism for units in the population. Statistically, this means that the sample inclusion indicator variable of the nonprobability sample and the outcome variable are independent given the set of auxiliary variables.

A2 Every unit in the target population has a non-zero probability of being included in the nonprobability sample.

A3 Units' participations in the nonprobability sample are independent of each other given the set of auxiliary variables. This means that, in a nonprobability sample, each person's decision to participate in the sample is not affected by what others decide given some auxiliary variables, e.g. some specific factors like age, gender, or other relevant variables.

Detail-box 10: Strong Ignorability Assumption (Rosenbaum and Rubin, 1983)

Let us define two samples: a probability sample S_A and a nonprobability sample S_B . Let us define the sample inclusion and participation indicator I_B as an indicator that takes value 1 if the unit i belongs to the sample S_B and 0 otherwise. Then, denote with $\pi_B(\mathbf{X}) = P(I_B = 1 | \mathbf{X})$ the sampling score, i.e., the probability of belonging to S_B given the common variables \mathbf{X} .

Strong ignorability assumption implies:

- (i) **Ignorability Assumption**(Rubin, 1976; Little and Rubin, 2002): the conditional independence of I_B and the study variable Y given the common variables \mathbf{X} .

$$\pi_B(\mathbf{X}) = P(I_B = 1 | \mathbf{X}, Y) = P(I_B = 1 | \mathbf{X})$$

- (ii) **Positivity Assumption:** $\pi_B(\mathbf{X})$ is strictly positive

$$\pi_{B,i}(\mathbf{X}) > 0, \quad \forall i$$

This assumption is valid when the set of variables \mathbf{X} includes all factors relevant for predicting the outcome Y influencing the probability of being chosen in sample S_B .

2.1.1. Propensity score weighting

The first method for combining probability and nonprobability samples is the so-called propensity score weighting (or adjustment) (Rosenbaum and Rubin, 1983). In this approach, the (unknown) probability of a unit being selected into the nonprobability sample, which is referred to as the propensity or sampling score, is modelled and estimated for all units in the nonprobability sample. The propensity scores for the nonprobability survey sample are theoretically defined for all the units in the target population. Estimation of propensity scores for units in the nonprobability sample requires an assumed model on the propensity scores and auxiliary information at the population level. Usually, the complete auxiliary information is not available, and under the setting assumed above (in which auxiliary information is available from an existing probability survey sample) the population auxiliary information is supplied by the reference probability sample. This leads to some differences in the estimation process. For example, when a parametric model is assumed, the maximum likelihood estimation method is replaced by the maximum pseudo-likelihood one. Three common parametric models are the logit model, the probit model, and the complementary log-log one. See Toy Example 3.1 for an illustration of the method. Non-parametric methods without assuming an explicit functional form for propensity scores can be an attractive alternative. The non-parametric kernel regression estimator for the propensity score is given by Yuan et al. (2022). Chu and Beaumont (2019) considered regression-tree-based method for estimating the propensity scores. Their method involving the combined sample of the nonprobability sample and the reference probability sample, seeks to build a classification tree. The terminal nodes of the final tree are employed as homogeneous groups in terms of propensity scores in a manner akin to post-stratification.

After the estimation of the propensity scores for the units in the nonprobability sample, the subsequent propensity score weights can be directly used to calculate one of the two versions of the inverse probability-weighted estimator (the adaptation of the Horvitz-Thompson estimator and the adaptation of the Hájek estimator for missing data problems and causal inference). Both these estimators may be sensitive to small values of estimated propensity scores. A robust alternative may be a post-stratified estimator in which the strata are formed based on homogeneous groups in terms of propensity scores.

In general, both the subsequent adjustments, propensity score weighting and stratification can be used to adjust for selection biases; see, e.g., Lee and Valliant (2009), Elliott (2017) and Chen et al. (2020). (Stuart et al., 2011, 2015) and Buchanan et al. (2018) used propensity score weighting to generalise results from randomised trials to a target population. O’Muircheartaigh and Hedges (2014) proposed propensity score stratification for analysing a non-randomised social experiment.

Finally, it is worth noting a weakness of the propensity score methods, is that they rely on a propensity score model (explicitly defined under the parametric approach) and are biased and highly variable if the model is misspecified (Kang and Schafer, 2007).

Toy Example 3.1: Propensity Score Weighting

The aim is to estimate μ_y , the average household's monthly energy consumption (Y).

- Assumption: Strong ignorability (Rosenbaum and Rubin, 1983)
- Approach:
 1. Propensity Score Model Definition: We need to define the *propensity score function*, namely a model for the probability of being in the nonprobability sample based on the auxiliary information. In this example, we want to specify the probability for an individual to belong to the dataset AB as a function of the available common variables: gender, age, annual utility expense, no. of household members, urban/rural classification, and type of dwelling. For the sake of simplicity, let us consider just one common variable, e.g., annual utility expense (X). For instance, we can use a parametric method, thus we can write

$$\text{logit}(\pi_{AB}(x_i)) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_X x_i, \quad \forall i.$$

2. Propensity Score Model Estimation:

If we assume the logit model specified above, we can estimate $\hat{\alpha}_0, \hat{\alpha}_X$, maximising the following pseudo-log-likelihood function (Chen et al., 2020). Note that the method requires the use of the pseudo-log-likelihood function instead of the log-likelihood function because the auxiliary information derives from a probability sample and not from the whole population.
3. Prediction: The unknown $\pi_{AB}(x_i)$ can be predicted for each unit i in the dataset AB.

To make inference using the nonprobability sample, for each unit in AB assign weights equal to the inverse of the estimated propensity scores.

- Outcome: Compute the weighted average of monthly energy consumption in the nonprobability sample AB as follows (adaptation of the Horvitz-Thompson estimator) :

$$\hat{\mu}_{IPW1} = N^{-1} \sum_{i \in AB} \frac{1}{\hat{\pi}_{AB}(x_i)} y_i$$

An alternative estimator (adaptation of the Hájek estimator) is given by:

$$\hat{\mu}_{IPW2} = \hat{N}_{AB}^{-1} \sum_{i \in AB} \frac{1}{\hat{\pi}_{AB}(x_i)} y_i$$

where $\hat{N}_{AB} = \sum_{i \in AB} (\hat{\pi}_{AB})^{-1}$

2.1.2. Calibration weighting

A second approach for combining probability and nonprobability samples uses calibration weighting (Deville and Särndal, 1992; Kott, 2006). This technique calibrates auxiliary information in the nonprobability sample with that in the probability sample, so that after calibration the weighted distribution of the nonprobability sample is similar to that of the target population. Rather than

estimating the propensity score model and inverting the propensity score to address the selection bias of the nonprobability sample, the calibration strategy directly estimates the weights. The justification of the calibration approach, by Deville and Särndal (1992), relies on the linearity of the model for the target variable or on the linearity of the inverse probability of sampling weight, but the linearity conditions are unlikely to hold for non-continuous variables. More in general, the robustness of the approach relies on the correct specification of the calibration approach. It should be noted that not everyone in the literature categorises this approach as a standalone method: at times, it is referred to as a weighting approach that encompasses both the propensity score and the calibration techniques. See Toy Example 3.2 for an illustration of the method.

Toy Example 3.2: Calibration weighting

The aim is to estimate μ_y , the average household's monthly energy consumption (Y).

- **Calibration Model:**
Use the annual utility expense as an auxiliary variable shared between the nonprobability (dataset AB) and probability survey samples (dataset P). We aim to calibrate the annual utility expense in the nonprobability dataset AB with that of the probability sample P so that after calibration dataset AB is similar to the target population.
- **Weight Adjustment:**
We directly estimate the weights. We assign a weight $\omega_{AB,i}$ to each unit i in the sample AB so that

$$\sum_{i \in AB} \omega_{AB,i} x_i = \sum_{i \in P} d_{P,i} x_i$$

$\sum_{i \in P} d_{P,i} x_i$ is a design-weighted estimate of the population total of X (annual utility expense) from the probability sample P ($d_{P,i}$ are inclusion probabilities). $\mathcal{Q}_{AB} = \{\omega_{AB,i} : i \in AB\}$ are the calibration weights we need to estimate. The balancing constraint calibrates the covariate distribution of the nonprobability sample (dataset AB) to the target population in terms of X. We are in an optimisation problem setting and the above is the covariate balancing constraint. We estimate \mathcal{Q}_{AB} by solving a constrained optimisation problem.

$$\min_{\mathcal{Q}_{AB}} \{L(\mathcal{Q}_{AB}) = \sum_{i \in AB} \omega_{AB,i} \log \omega_{AB,i}\}$$

subject to $\omega_{AB,i} \geq 0$ for all $i \in AB$, $\sum_{i \in AB} \omega_{AB,i} = N$ and the balancing constraint.

- **Outcome:**
Calculate the weighted average of the monthly energy consumption in the dataset AB (adaptation of the Horvitz-Thompson estimator).

$$\hat{\mu}_{cal1} = N^{-1} \sum_{i \in AB} \omega_{AB,i} y_i$$

An alternative estimator (adaptation of the Hájek estimator) is given by:

$$\hat{\mu}_{cal2} = \hat{N}_{AB}^{-1} \sum_{i \in AB} \omega_{AB,i} y_i$$

where $\hat{N}_{AB} = \sum_{i \in AB} \omega_{AB,i}$

2.1.3. Mass imputation

The third method is the mass imputation or prediction approach, which imputes the missing values for all units in the probability sample. In the usual imputation for missing data analysis, the respondents in the sample constitute a training dataset for developing an imputation model. In the mass imputation, an independent nonprobability sample is used as a training dataset for developing the imputation model, and imputation is applied to all units in the probability sample; see, e.g., Breidt et al. (1996); Rivers (2007); Kim and Rao (2012); Chipperfield et al. (2012); Bethlehem (2016); Yang and Kim (2018). Different imputation models, parametric and non-parametric, have been suggested in the literature, the choice depends on the nature of the response variable but also on the type and quantity of auxiliary variables available for both samples (probability and nonprobability). Brick (2015) discussed diagnostics and model checking.

After imputing the values of the response variable for the units in the probability sample, these values, along with the weights associated with the units in the probability sample (i.e., the reciprocal of the inclusion probabilities), are used to calculate a design-based estimator for the descriptive parameter of interest. See Toy Example 3.3 for an illustration of the method. The consistency of this estimator relies on a correct specification of the imputation model and of the estimate of the model parameters.

Toy Example 3.3: Mass Imputation

The aim is to estimate μ_y , the average household's monthly energy consumption (Y). For the sake of simplicity, one could consider just one common variable, e.g., annual utility expense (X).

- Assumptions: strong ignorability (Rosenbaum and Rubin, 1983).
- Approach: Mass imputation.

1. Model estimation: Let us specify a model for the monthly energy consumption as a function of the annual utility expense.

$$\log(y_i) = \beta_0 + \beta_X x_i + \varepsilon_i, \quad \forall i \in AB.$$

We use the observations i in dataset AB to obtain the estimates $\hat{\beta}_0, \hat{\beta}_X$.

- Prediction: We use the estimates $\hat{\beta}_0, \hat{\beta}_X$ to predict \hat{y}_j for $j \in P$.
- Outcome: We define the following mass imputation estimator, which allows us to compute the average monthly energy consumption in dataset P:

$$\hat{\mu}_I = N^{-1} \sum_{j \in P} d_{P,j} \hat{y}_j,$$

where $d_{P,j}$ are the design-weights of sample P.

2.1.4. Doubly Robust Procedure

To improve the robustness against model misspecification, this approach combines the weighting and the imputation approaches, employing both the propensity score and the outcome model.

The Doubly Robust (DR) estimator of the mean is composed of two terms, one is the model-based prediction of the mean (i.e. corresponds to the estimator used adopting the mass imputation approach), the other is a propensity score-based adjustment using the errors given by the differences between the observed and model-predicted response for the units in nonprobability sample. See Toy Example 3.4 for an illustration of the method. The magnitude of the adjustment term is negatively correlated to the goodness of fit of the outcome model. Consequently, the DR estimator is unbiased if either the propensity score model or the outcome model is correctly specified, but not necessarily both. Moreover, it is important to note that its double robustness property does not require the knowledge of which of the two models is correctly specified. This estimator has been proposed by Chen et al. (2020) under the two-sample setting assumed at the beginning of the section, and assuming a logistic model for the propensity score and a parametric regression model for the outcome. Note that the DB mean estimator suggested by Chen et al. (2020), is analogous to the model-assisted generalised difference estimator discussed in Wu and Sitter (2001) under scenarios where the complete (i.e. at the population level) auxiliary information is available.

Recently, Chen et al. (2022) suggested an alternative approach to produce a double robust estimator by using the pseudo empirical likelihood method and considering both the normalisation constraint (on the probability measure over the units in the nonprobability sample) and the model calibration constraint (on an assumed outcome regression model).

Toy Example 3.4: Double Robust Procedure

The aim is to estimate μ_y , the average household's monthly energy consumption (Y). For the sake of simplicity, one could consider just one common variable, e.g., annual utility expense (X).

- Assumptions: strong ignorability (Rosenbaum and Rubin, 1983)
- Approach: Double Robust Inference
It employs both the propensity score function (Section ??) and the outcome models (Section ??) to improve the robustness of the estimator.
- Outcome:
Let's compute the average monthly energy consumption by using the Double Robust estimator:

$$\hat{\mu}_{dr} = \hat{N}_{AB}^{-1} \sum_{i \in AB} \frac{1}{\hat{\pi}_{AB,i}(x_i)} \{y_i - \hat{y}_i\} + \hat{N}_P^{-1} \sum_{j \in P} d_{P,j} \hat{y}_j$$

where $\hat{N}_{AB} = \sum_{i \in AB} (\hat{\pi}_{AB})^{-1}$ and $\hat{N}_P = \sum_{j \in P} d_{P,i}$

2.2. Combining probability sampling and big data

In the past decade, more and more data became available, including large administrative record datasets, remote-sensing data derived from satellite images (McRoberts et al., 2010), mobile sensor data (Palmer et al., 2013), and web survey panels (Tourangeau et al., 2013). While such data sources provide timely data for a large number of variables and population elements, they are nonprobability samples and often fail to represent the target population of interest because of inherent selection biases. Thus, it is essential to combine such data with probability samples. How to combine such information with survey data to provide better estimates for the population parameters is a new challenge that survey statisticians face today. Tam and Clarke (2015) presented an overview of some initiatives of big data applications in official statistics of the Australian Bureau of Statistics.

Depending on the roles in statistical inference, big data can be classified into two types: one with large sample sizes (large n) and the other with a rich set of covariates (large p). In the first type, the nonprobability sample can be large in sample size. How to leverage the rich information in the big data to improve finite population inference is an important research topic that needs to be explored. In the second type, there are a large number of variables. There is a vast literature on variable selection methods for prediction, but very few contributions on variable selection for data integration that can successfully recognise the strengths and the limitations of each data source and utilise all captured information for finite population inference.

In cases where nonprobability data have large sample sizes (large n), it is crucial to differentiate between two scenarios based on whether the response variable is observed in the probability sample or not:

- When the probability sample includes the response variable, its mean, total, or other related parameters can be estimated by the commonly used estimator solely from the probability sample. In this situation, the auxiliary information in the big data can be used to improve this estimator. A common framework is to assume that the membership to the big data can be determined throughout the probability sample. Additionally, it is assumed the subsample of units in the probability sample constitutes a second-phase sample from the big data sample, which acts as a new population. Consequently, it is possible to calibrate the information in the second-phase sample to be the same as the new acting population. This idea has been explored by Yang and Ding (2020) and Kim and Tam (2021) among others. Kim and Tam (2021) have also implemented their calibration method, to incorporate big data auxiliary information, on the official statistics from the Australian Bureau of Statistics.
- When the response variable is present in the big dataset, but not in the probability sample, the situation is equivalent to the one described for combining probability and nonprobability samples. Hence, the same solution may be applied. Currently, the prevailing approach is mass imputation, wherein a predictive model is trained using big data and subsequently employed to impute the values of the response variable in the probability sample. Beyond parametric methods, nonparametric approaches such as nearest-neighbor imputation can also be considered (Yang and Kim, 2018). In the international forest inventory community, for combining ground-based observations with images from remote sensors, is popular to use a K-nearest-neighbour imputation strategy in which instead of using one nearest neighbour,

multiple nearest neighbours in the big data sample is identified, and the average response is used as the imputed value (McRoberts et al., 2010).

In the presence of big data of the second type, where there is a large number of auxiliary variables (large p), variable selection becomes crucial. This is essential for discerning the strengths and limitations of each data source and ensuring the utilisation of all and only the information relevant to inference about the finite population. With a large number of auxiliary variables existing integration methods may become unstable or even infeasible, since adding irrelevant auxiliary variables can introduce a large variability in the estimation. Gao and Carroll (2017) proposed a pseudo-likelihood approach for combining multiple non-survey data with high dimensionality; this approach requires all likelihoods to be correctly specified and therefore is sensitive to model misspecification. Chen et al. (2018) proposed a model-based calibration approach using LASSO; this approach relies on a correctly specified outcome model. Yang (2020) proposed a doubly robust variable selection and estimation strategy that works in two steps. In the first step, it selects a set of variables that are important predictors of either the sampling score or the outcome model using penalised estimating equations. In the second step, it re-estimates the models' parameters by using the joint set of covariates selected from the first step and calculates the doubly robust estimator. This double robust estimator allows model misspecification of either the sampling score or the outcome model. Moreover, in the existing highdimensional causal inference literature, the doubly robust estimators have been shown to be robust to selection errors using penalisation (Farrell, 2015) or approximation errors using machine learning (Chernozhukov et al., 2018).

3. Implementation

This section provides useful information for the implementation of the methods described so far. The blue boxes below, one for each method introduced in this report, include the main packages for the most common software - R, Stata, and Python. For a general overview of the methods typically used in official and survey statistics that are implemented in R, see the CRAN Task View "CRAN Task View: Official Statistics & Survey Statistics"⁵. The task view is split into several parts:

- First part: "Producing Official Statistics". This first part is targeted at people working at national statistical institutes, national banks, international organizations, etc. who are involved in the production of official statistics and using methods from survey statistics.
- Second part: "Access to Official Statistics". This second part's target audience is everyone interested in using official statistics results directly from within R.
- Third part: "Related Methods" shows packages that are important in official and survey statistics, but do not directly fit into the production of official statistics.

⁵ CRAN Task View: Official Statistics & Survey Statistics: <https://cran.r-project.org/web/views/OfficialStatistics.html>

Tools for Record Linkage

- [abeR](#) is an R package available on GitHub that makes allowance for errors in the data by not requiring matches to be exact. It uses an algorithm that specifies a set of decision rules to determine whether two records are sufficiently similar for them to be considered a match. A related [Stata code](#) is also available. The codes are based on methods described in Abramitzky et al. (2012, 2014, 2019).
- AMP is a met suggests a fully automated probabilistic method for linking historical datasets. The authors estimate these probabilities using the Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm. They suggest a number of decision rules that use these estimated probabilities to determine which records to use in the analysis. You can find the R code and Stata code on their [website](#). The codes are based on methods described in Abramitzky et al. (2020).
- [blink](#) is an R package performing Bayesian entity resolution for categorical and text data, for any distance function defined by the user. In addition, the package allow the comparison to any other comparable method such as logistic regression, Bayesian additive regression trees (BART), or random forests. The package is based on the bipartite graph model by Steorts (2015).
- [Dedupe](#) is a Python library that uses machine learning to perform fuzzy matching, deduplication and entity resolution quickly on structured data. For more details on the methods offered by the package, see (Gregg and Eder, 2022).

Tools for Record Linkage

- [fastLink](#) is an R package that implements a Fellegi-Sunter probabilistic record linkage model that accommodates missing data and integrates auxiliary information. The software provides features for merging two datasets using the Fellegi-Sunter model, employing the Expectation-Maximization algorithm. The package is based on methods described in Enamorado et al. (2019)
- [fedmatch](#) (Fast, Flexible, and User-Friendly Record Linkage Methods) is a R package which provides a flexible set of tools for matching two unlinked datasets. It allows for three ways to match data: exact matches, fuzzy matches, and multi-variable matches. It also allows an easy combination of these three matches. You can find details on the package in the technical paper, Lee (2021).
- [Reclin2](#) is an R package implementing functions to assist in performing probabilistic record linkage and deduplication (i.e., generating pairs, comparing records, em-algorithm for estimating m - and u -probabilities (Fellegi and Sunter, 1969)). It allows also for pre- and post-processing for machine learning methods for record linkage.
- [RecordLinkage](#) is an R package implementing methods based on a stochastic approach and classification algorithms from the ML domain. For details, see Sariyar and Borg (2016).
- [Record Linkage](#) is a Python toolkit that provides most of the tools needed for record linkage and deduplication. The package contains indexing methods, functions to compare records and classifiers, and it is developed for research and the linking of small or medium-sized files. For more information on the methods implemented in the toolkit see de Bruin (2017).
- [RELAIS](#) (REcord Linkage At IStat) is an open source toolkit providing a set of techniques for dealing with record linkage projects elaborated by Istat (Italian national statistical institute).
- [Splink](#) is a Python package for probabilistic record linkage that allows you to deduplicate and link records from datasets that lack unique identifiers. For more details on the methods offered by the package, see Linacre et al. (2022).

Tools for Statistical Matching

- **MatchIt** is an R package performing matching, with a focus on the causal inference setting.
- `smpc` and `smmatch` commands in Stata perform Statistical Matching based on Alpmann (2016), that implements the statistical matching procedure proposed by Rubin (1986).
- **StatMatch** is an R package for data integration through statistical matching and, as a by-product, the ability to impute missing values in a dataset.

Tools for estimation in nonprobability samples

- **NonProbEst** is an R package which implements a set of techniques for estimation in non-probability surveys, using various approaches. Functions in the package allow to obtain calibration weights, propensity scores and matching predictions for a reference sample. Machine learning classification algorithms can be used as alternatives for logistic regression as a technique to estimate propensities. For more details on the implementation, see Rueda et al. (2020)
- **nonprobsvy** is an R package available on GitHub; the package provides the implementation of modern methods for nonprobability samples when auxiliary information from the population or probability sample is available. The methods available are inverse probability weighting estimators with possible calibration constraints Chen et al. (2020), mass imputation estimators based on nearest neighbours (Yang et al., 2021), predictive mean matching and regression imputation (Kim et al., 2021), doubly robust estimators with bias minimization (Yang, 2020). Tutorials can be found at [this link](#).

4 Conclusions

Throughout the last few decades, national statistical agencies and international organisations have relied heavily on sample surveys to produce crucial statistical information. Surveys have played an essential role in providing reliable, accurate, and regularly updated data. However, due to the high costs of probabilistic surveys and the decline in response rates it has become increasingly challenging, if not impossible, to obtain comprehensive and up-to-date information on the phenomena of interest through traditional investigation techniques based on probability samples. Moreover, many of these phenomena urge to be measured in a timely and granular manner, e.g., among others, climate change, pollution, social inclusion, poverty.

Data coming from a variety of non-probabilistic large-scale observations, such as digital administrative records, satellite data, and web data, have the potential to complement and enrich traditional data sources. These alternative data sources, that are becoming increasingly available and affordable, yet differ in their characteristics, levels of detail, and degrees of quality.

From these considerations arises the challenge of developing new statistical methods to appropriately combine data from multiple sources in order to make use of all the available information on a specific phenomenon under study.

In recent years, numerous researchers have made significant contributions in the domain of data integration methods in official statistics and survey methodology. However, the dissemination of these refined techniques is proving difficult among non-statisticians. This report provides an insight into the challenges and opportunities associated with various topics of data integration, such as record linkage, statistical matching, and probability and non-probability sample combination, providing a comprehensive overview for a broader audience interested in this evolving landscape of statistical methods. Thought for a multidisciplinary audience, each topic's presentation is intentionally kept non-technical and enriched with toy/practical examples to illustrate the various methods presented. Additionally, for each method, the primary packages for the most common software - R, Stata, and Python - are indicated.

The flowchart in the Appendix can be a useful tool to guide the reader in the identification of the most appropriate method according to the characteristics of the available data and the purposes for which the integration is being done.

5 Appendix

Figure 5: Flowchart: Data Integration methods

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